

CRUISE OPERATIONAL REPORT

MOMARSAT 2023

WORKING AREA - LUCKY STRIKE

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE – EMSO-AZORES

RV L'ATALANTE

SUBMERSIBLE VICTOR6000

Photo J. Sarrazin

Cruise chief scientist : Marjolaine MATABOS, Ifremer

Infrastructure Manager: Laurent GAUTIER

Project manager: Mathilde CANNAT, IPGP- CNRS

Made available: 07/10/2023

Demobilization:

29/07/23

Number of

Port of departure:

HORTA, ACORES

Port of arrival:

HORTA, ACORES

days 20

Table des matières

1.	Permissions.....	4
2.	Objectives and description of the work	4
3.	Position of the infrastructure components	7
4.	Work area and maps.....	10
5.	Scientific and technical crew	11
6.	Operations timeline.....	13
7.	Dive summaries.....	17
7.1.	MoMARSAT 2023 Dive 839-1.....	17
7.1.1.	Objectives.....	17
7.1.2.	Operations summary	17
7.1.3.	Moorings	20
7.1.4.	Samples	21
7.1.5.	Measurements.....	21
7.1.6.	Navigation	23
7.2.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 840-2.....	24
7.2.1.	Objectives.....	24
7.2.2.	Operations summary	24
7.2.3.	Moorings.....	25
7.2.4.	Samples	26
7.2.5.	Measurements.....	26
7.2.6.	Navigation	27
7.3.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 841-3.....	28
7.3.1.	Objectives.....	28
7.3.2.	Operations summary	28
7.3.3.	Moorings.....	28
7.3.4.	Samples	29
7.3.5.	Measurements.....	29
7.3.6.	Navigation.....	29
7.4.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 842-4.....	30
7.4.1.	Objectives.....	30
7.4.2.	Operations summary:	30
7.4.3.	Moorings	33
7.4.4.	Samples	33
7.4.5.	Measurements.....	34
	Navigation	34
7.5.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 843-5.....	35
7.5.1.	Objectives.....	35
7.5.2.	Operation summary:	35
7.5.3.	Samples	35
7.6.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 844-6.....	36
7.6.1.	Objectives.....	36
7.6.2.	Operations summary:	36
7.6.3.	Moorings	41
7.6.4.	Samples	41
7.6.5.	Measurements.....	42
7.6.6.	Reconstruction 3.....	43
7.6.7.	OTUS	43
7.6.8.	Navigation	44
7.7.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 845-7.....	45
7.7.1.	Objectives.....	45
7.7.2.	Operations summary:	45
7.7.3.	Moorings.....	46
7.7.4.	Samples	47
7.7.5.	Measurements.....	47
7.7.6.	Navigation.....	48
7.8.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 846-8.....	49
7.8.1.	Objectives.....	49
7.8.2.	Operations summary	49
7.8.3.	Moorings	51
7.8.4.	Samples	51

7.8.5.	Measurements.....	51
7.8.6.	Navigation	52
7.9.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 847-9.....	53
7.9.1.	Objectives.....	53
7.9.2.	Operations summary:	53
7.9.3.	Moorings	54
7.9.4.	Samples	54
7.9.5.	Measurements.....	54
7.9.6.	OTUS	54
7.9.7.	Navigation	54
7.10.	MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 848-10.....	54
7.10.1.	Objectives.....	54
7.10.2.	Operations summary:	55
7.10.3.	Moorings	56
7.10.4.	Samples	57
7.10.5.	Measurements.....	57
7.10.6.	OTUS	57
7.10.7.	Navigation	57
8.	Operations.....	58
8.1.	Operations and surface moorings	58
8.2.	CTD casts.....	59
8.3.	Moorings recovered or installed during the cruise with the ROV VICTOR	60
8.4.	Liste des prélèvements	63
8.4.1.	Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS).....	63
8.4.2.	Biological sampling.....	63
8.4.3.	Fluid sampling	64
8.5.	Continuous measurements	66

This document presents the operations carried out and lists the samples taken during the campaign. MoMARSAT 2023. DOI [10.17600/18002419](https://doi.org/10.17600/18002419)

1. Permissions

Copies of the documents are presented in the appendix.

Ref NV 86621/2023	Ministerio dos Negocios Estrangeiros	Nota Verbal (traduction française en fin de document)
AMP / 2023 / 007	REGIAO AUTONOMA DOS AÇORES Secretaria Regional do Mar Ciência e Tecnologia Direcao Regional Dos Assuntos do Mar	<i>AUTHORIZATION AREA FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN MARINE PROTECTED AREA</i>
CCIR- RAA/2023/35 + Addenda	REGIAO AUTONOMA DOS AÇORES Vice-Presidência do Governo dos Açores/Direção Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia Direção Acesso e utilização de recursos naturais para fins científicos	Declaracao de Conforidade Access and use of natural resources for scientific purinstallings

2. Objectives and description of the work

The MoMARSAT cruises series (doi.org/10.18142/130) provides annual maintenance of the EMSO-Azores Observatory at the Lucky Strike hydrothermal field. This seafloor observatory has been operating since 2010 and aims to acquire time series >10 years of hydrothermal, tectonic and volcanic processes and vent ecosystems on an active hydrothermal vent field on the mid-Atlantic ridge. It is part of the European network EMSO ERIC (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory - <http://emso.eu/>), supported in France by the EMSO-FR Research Infrastructure (MESR) which management is ensured by a collaboration Ifremer- CNRS.

The array includes an observatory infrastructure: two junction boxes (SEAMON) at the bottom which connect instruments (Fig. 1). This year, the surface buoy (BOREL2) ensuring the transfer of data, by satellite, to a server on land as well as communication with the connected instruments was removed as part of the approach towards an operational maintenance. In its current configuration (after MOMARSAT 2023 maintenance), the “connected” part of the observatory includes: a seismometer (OBS), a generic environmental measurement module (EGIM equipped with a CTD, hydrophone, oxygen sensor, turbidimeter, pressure gauge and ADCP), a biological observation module (TEMPO- with an HDTV camera and 2 projectors), an oxygen sensor, a turbidity sensor and four hydrophones (temporarily disconnected for repair). The device also includes autonomous instruments which store their data internally: 4 OBS, 2 pressure sensors, 29 autonomous temperature probes deployed within smokers and diffusion areas, 5 autonomous current meters arranged, 6 microbiological colonizers, and 9 biological colonizers. These “unconnected” elements extend the spatial coverage of monitoring during each maintenance.

The maintenance operations consisted in the replacement replacing of the BOREL-SEAMON infrastructure and connected instruments, their reconditioning on board, and their redeployment. This

year the Borel buoy and the oceanographic mooring were not redeployed. *In situ* sampling of rocks, fluid, fauna, microorganisms and the acquisition of imaging transects on targeted sites allow multi-year monitoring of the system and supplement the infrastructure data. These measurements also make it possible to calibrate/validate the measurements carried out by the instrumental array. This year, bottom operations were carried out by the Victor6000 submersible.

CTD Depiles in the water column provided inter-calibration of the ocean mooring sensors and the monitoring of the plume near the bottom. Shipborne ADCP transects were carried out towards the east of the ridge and an MBS acquisition was carried out on the return transit for the Portuguese authorities.

Note that the landing of an elevator dead weight on the Hydrocoptus cable of Hydro 2 may have damaged the system, its replacement will have to be considered during the 2024 campaign.

Figure 1. Map of the Lucky Strike area on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (left) et the observatory design with two bottom seafloor anodes and the surface buoy (right).

Related projects

The MoMARSAT 2023 campaign and the EMSO-Azores observatory are part of the following projects:

- **EMSO ERIC** (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory, www.emso-eu.org/, DG J. Danobeitia)
- **EU H2020 iAtlantic** (<http://www.iatlantic.eu/>, coordinator M. Roberts University of Edinburgh, grant agreement No 818123). MoMARSAT missions contribute to WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. Repeated visits allow the acquisition of images and environmental measurements used for spatio-temporal mapping of habitats and biological communities (WP2, WP3). The data acquired will contribute to calibrating high-resolution hydrodynamic models (WP1). In 2023, a collaboration with Telmo Morato (Univ. Azores) will contribute to completing the mapping of the area as part of **Seabed 2030**
- **Deep-Rest** (European BIODITOWARDSA project, coordinator J. Sarrazin, Ifremer). This project aims to develop new approaches to inform environmental managers. The mission will contribute to the implementation of experiments to evaluate the growth rate of dominant species and the response of communities to a plume of hydrothermal sediment.
- **Lifedeeper** (PPR project, coordination by MA Cambon, Ifremer) also aims to inform environmental conservation strategies in the context of deep mining. Acquiring images and sampling individuals will help to better understand the distribution of species and connectivity along the ridge.
- **Abyssex**: Pressurized aquarium displaying crabs and shrimps collected from the Lucky Strike hydrothermal field to the general public. PI D. Barthélemy (Océanopolis). *Segonzacia mesatlantica* crabs and *Mirocaris fortunata* shrimps were collected, kept alive and transferred to Brest to

Océanopolis for the general public exhibition “Abyssbox” started in 2012 in collaboration with the University of Paris Sorbonne (UPMC) and Ifremer.

- **ANR IRONWOMAN** (ANR-21-CE02-0012, PI C. Rommevaux 2021-2025): the sampling of iron-rich microbial mats will make it possible to validate the hypothesis of the primordial role of marine iron-oxidizing bacteria (FeOB) in the development of iron-rich mats, and the impact on iron biogeochemical cycle and primary production in the deep oceans, in relation to variations in the environmental conditions.
- **ANR HotHg**: fluid samples help evaluate the fluxes, speciation and transformation of mercury at hydrothermal vents
- **SMASH**: an experiment was deployed in 2021 to study the degradation of polymers biodegradable. Some of these samples will be recovered this year.

The coordination of maintenance operations and the initial use of data is ensured by Mathilde Cannat (EMSO-France manager) and Pierre Marie Sarradin (responsible for the Azores node). The management of operations on board was ensured this year by Marjolaine Matabos, and Laurent Gautier. The data acquired during the cruises are available on the portal <http://www.emso-fr.org/fr/EMSO-Azores>. The study area is part of the Portuguese EEZ and a “Marine Protected Area” (OSPAR).

3. Position of the infrastructure components

Table 1 : Position of the different constituents of the infrastructure after the 2023 maintenance campaign

Name	Locality	date	Dive	Latitude - Longitude	Depth	Description
BT11	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.332 W 032 16.532	1698	Autonomous temperature probe
BT12	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.336 W 032 16.536	1697	Autonomous temperature probe
BT13	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.332 W 032 16.532	1698	Autonomous temperature probe
Cage G12/24	Montsegur	16/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.285 W 032 16.533	1701	Gastropod cage
Cage M12/24	Tour Eiffel	16/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.339 W 032 16.543	1694	Cage mussels
Cage M36	Tour Eiffel	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.338 W 032 16.547	1693	Cage mussels
Colonizer ANA_1	Sintra	17/06/2022	2034-7	N 37 17.510 W 032 16.470		Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_2	Sintra	17/06/2022	2034-7	N 37 17.510 W 032 16.470		Wildlife colonizer
ANA_3 colonizer	Sintra	17/06/2022	2034-7	N 37 17.510 W 032 16.470		Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_4	Saemon W	18/06/2022	2035-8	N 37 17.500 W 032 16.700		Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_5	Seamon W	18/06/2022	2035-8	N 37 17.500 W 032 16.700		Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_6	Seamon W	18/06/2022	2035-8	N 37 17.500 W 032 16.700		Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_7	JPPE	20/06/2022	2037-10			Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_8	JPPE	20/06/2022	2037-10			Wildlife colonizer
Colonizer ANA_9	JPPE	20/06/2022	2037-10			Wildlife colonizer
LSLL2 Colonizer	Lava lake	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.544 W 032 16.795	1738	Microbial colonizer
LSNTE1 colonizer	Tour Eiffel N	16/07/2023	841-3	N 37 17.354 W 032 16.540	1690	Microbial colonizer
LSY3-1 Colonizer	Y3FeOx	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.512 W 032 16.670	1728	Microbial colonizer
LSSW1 colonizer	Sintra FeOx	23/07/2023	845-7	N 37 17.544 W 032 16.491	1619	Microbial colonizer
LSCap6 Colonizer	Capelinhos	21/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.368 W 032 15.834	1668	Microbial colonizer
COMBO 2	Tour Eiffel	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.348 W 032 16.538	1687	Bell incubation
HTNKE29008	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.333 W 032 16.540	1694	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29009	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.322 W 032 16.522	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29014	Montsegur	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.288 W 032 16.546	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29016	Cypress	26/07/2023	848-10	N 37 17.456 W 032 16.848	1744	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30001	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.329 W 032 16.540	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30002	White Castle	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.388 W 032 16.869	1712	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30007	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.329 W 032 16.540	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30012	Montsegur	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.284 W 032 16.525	1700	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30015	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.359 W 032 16.533	1688	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE41001	White Castle	23/07/2023	846-8	N 37 17.389 W 032 16.861	1721	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE41003	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.336 W 032 16.546	1697	Autonomous temperature probe
HTW005	White Castle	23/07/2023	846-8	N 37 17.381 W 032 16.867	1708	Autonomous temperature probe
HTWN021	Montsegur	24/07/2023	846-8	N 37 17.282 W 032 16.536	1699	Stand-alone temperature probe
JPPE		18/06/2022	2035-8			Pressure sensor
JPPW		20/06/2022	2037-10			Pressure sensor
LTgrad1	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.361 W 032 16.528	1689	Stand-alone temperature probe

LTgrad2	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.346 W 032 16.515	1691	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad3	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.326 W 032 16.522	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad5	White Castle	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.402 W 032 16.867	1720	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad6	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.341 W 032 16.511	1700	Autonomous temperature probe
LT grade8	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.329 W 032 16.539	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad9	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.337 W 032 16.574	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad10	Lucky strike	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.338 W 032 16.514	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad13	Tour Eiffel	13/07/2023	839-1	N 37 17.331 W 032 16.541	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad15	Tour Eiffel	15/07/2023	840-2	N 37 17.339 W 032 16.546	1694	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad20	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.327 W 032 16.528	1697	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad21	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.329 W 032 16.544	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
LTi1	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.341 W 032 16.546	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
LTW003	South Crystal	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.437 W 032 16.932	1720	Autonomous temperature probe
LTW017	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.338 W 032 16.524	1691	Autonomous temperature probe
LTW018	South Crystal	17/07/2023	842-4	N 37 17.436 W 032 16.934	1720	Autonomous temperature probe
Seamon is	Tour Eiffel	26/07/2023	848-10	N 37 17.329 W 032 16.532	1696	Bottom station
Simon West	Lucky strike	24/07/2023	847-9	N 37 17.474 W 032 16.784	1737	Bottom station
SMASH cylinder	Seamon W	24/07/2023	847-9	N 37 17.473 W 032 16.788	1738	Aging experiment
OBS Seamon West	Lucky strike	25/07/2023	847-9	N 37 17.469 W 032 16.790	1739	OBS
NOTE-LSVWQ	Lucky strike	17/07/2023		N 37 17.93292 W 032 19.54104 2037		OBS
NOTE-LSVSQ	Lucky strike	18/07/2023		N 37 15.6235 W 032 17.8666	1925	OBS
NOTE-LSVEQ	Lucky strike	17/07/2023		N 37 16.85448 W 032 14.4813	1883	OBS
OBS-LSVNQ	Lucky strike	18/07/2023		N 37 19.1476 W 032 16.8466	1800	OBS
TIME	Tour Eiffel	26/07/2023	848-10	N 37 17.325 W 032 16.537	1699	Observation module
TCM3-2	Seamon W	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.449 W 032 16.907	1739	Current meter
TCM3-A	Tour Eiffel	22/07/2023	845-7	N 37 17.348 W 032 16.535	1689	Current meter (in a hole)
TCM3-B	Tour Eiffel	20/06/2023	844-6	N 37 17.340 W 032 16.540	1694	Current meter
TCM3-C	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.336 W 032 16.533	1691	Current meter
TCM3-D	Tour Eiffel	20/07/2023	844-6	N 37 17.349 W 032 16.534	1690	Current meter

4. Work area and maps

Map of the area and position of moorings after Momarsat 2022 and extent of the work zone

Instrumentation on the Eiffel Tower and Montségur after Momarsat 2022

Mertz	Nicolas	M	Electronics	Ifremer	X					X									
Chauvet	Adrien	M	Electronics	Ifremer	X					X									
Saliou	Damien	M	Mecanics	Ifremer	X					X									
Bocher	Alan	M	Maintenance	Ifremer	X					X									
Rommevaux	Céline	F	Géomicrobiologie	CNRS/MIO	X					X									
Lemaréchal	Cyprien	M	Physique	UBO	X						X								
Cuvelier	Daphne	F	Ecology	Azores Unitowardsity		X				X									
Fournier	Pierre-Yves	M	Operational chief	Genavir										X					
Fauvin	Olivier	M	Electronicien	Genavir										X					
Frémont	Yoann	M	Electronicien	Genavir										X					
Romain	Julien	M	Mécanicien	Genavir										X					
Lajoie	David	M	Electronicien	Genavir															
Canessa	Julien	M	Electronicien	Genavir										X					
Bartoloni	Nathan	M	Electronicien	Genavir										X					
Jimenez-Jimenez	Cédric	M	Mécanicien	Genavir															
Levy	Sami	M	Mécanicien	Genavir										X					

a. **M/F** : Enter the gender of the person.

b. **Discipline**: Geology, physics, chemistry, biology, mechanics, electronics, computer science, etc.

c. **The reporting organization** is the one for which the scientist works: **F** : France, **EU** : European Union, **E** : Europe outside the European Union, **A** : Other countries

d. **CH.** : Researcher, **I/T**: Engineers / Technicians, **D**: Doctoral student, **AND**: Student, **P. S**: Sedentary staff of the Genavir operator (excluding ship operating sailors),
A: Journalists, obsertowards, technicians of the scientific team...

e. **Leg** : Mention presence on board, according to the dates given on the first page.

6. Operations timeline

This table lists the chronology of surface operations and dives carried out during the cruise (Extraction from Casino and SEALOG software). Data missing due to CINNA acquisition problem.

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Nom apbyeil	Code instrum	Nom action	Identificateur Opération	Comment
12/07/2023	19:10:40	N 37 16.835	W 032 14.491	Navire	NAV	Transit	MOM23NAV1	Arrival sur site
12/07/2023	19:15:00	N 37 16.825	W 032 14.487	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release acoustique	MOM23OBS1	LSVEP
12/07/2023	20:34:00	N 37 16.775	W 032 14.327	Autonomous OBS	OBS	At the surface	MOM23OBS2	LSVEP
12/07/2023	21:48:00	N 37 16.851	W 032 14.525	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Mooring	MOM23OBS3	Mooring by Winch Bathy : LSVEQ
12/07/2023	23:18:00	N 37 16.844	W 032 14.537	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release OBS	MOM23OBS4	
13/07/2023	00:40:00	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.327	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Winch onboard	MOM23OBS5	Winch Bathy
13/07/2023	01:25:00	N 37 17.374	W 032 16.499	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPW	Mooring	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW1	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON W
13/07/2023	04:14:00	N 37 17.515	W 032 16.747	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPW	Release flottabilité	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW2	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON W
13/07/2023	05:20:00	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.748	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPW	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW3	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON W
13/07/2023	06:22:00	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.436	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE1	
13/07/2023	07:20:20	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.633	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV1	PL1
13/07/2023	09:01:00	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.779	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV2	
13/07/2023	16:07:00	N 37 17.249	W 032 16.474	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE6	NAVI1
13/07/2023	16:47:10	N 37 17.099	W 032 16.629	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE7	
13/07/2023	17:05:50	N 37 17.168	W 032 16.741	Elevator	ASCE	Onboard	MOM23ASCE8	
14/07/2023	06:05:00			VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom		
14/07/2023	07:09:30			VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV	
14/07/2023	07:50:30	N 37 17.568	W 032 16.672	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV3 -	Fin PL1
14/07/2023	08:30:30	N 37 17.473	W 032 17.155	SEAMON W	FLOTTARECUPW	Release	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW4	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON W
14/07/2023	09:00:10	N 37 17.397	W 032 17.098	SEAMON W	FLOTTARECUPW	Surface	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW5	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON W
14/07/2023	10:24:40	N 37 17.149	W 032 16.409	SEAMON W	FLOTTARECUPW	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPW6	Recovery buoyancy SEAMONW
14/07/2023	12:00:10	N 37 17.368	W 032 16.467	Elevator		Mooring	MOM23ASCE9	NAVI2
14/07/2023	14:48:40	N 37 17.050	W 032 16.888	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Mooring	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE1	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est N37°17,319 - W32°16,558
14/07/2023	17:49:00	N 37 17.376	W 032 16.508	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Release station	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE2	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
14/07/2023	18:39:00	N 37 17.432	W 032 16.490	Cable Grand Fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE3	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
14/07/2023	19:31:00	N 37 17.124	W 032 16.579	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV4	PL2
15/07/2023	05:58:00			VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom		
15/07/2023	06:00:00			Elevator	ASCE	Release		
15/07/2023	06:51:00			Elevator	ASCE	Onboard		
15/07/2023	07:15:00			VICTOR	ROV	At the surface		
15/07/2023	07:58:50	N 37 17.426	W 032 16.485	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV5	fin PL2
15/07/2023	09:25:00			BOREL		Release		
15/07/2023	09:41:00			BOREL		Fixation on board		
15/07/2023	10:30:00			BOREL		Onboard		
15/07/2023	12:56:00			BOREL		Onboard		Fin recuperation BOREL
15/07/2023	14:16:20	N 37 17.455	W 032 17.163	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	Release	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE4	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
15/07/2023	15:00:40	N 37 17.125	W 032 16.627	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	At the surface	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE5	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Nom abpyeil	Code instrum	Nom action	Identificateur Opération	Comment
15/07/2023	16:15:20	N 37 16.554	W 032 15.257	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE6	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
15/07/2023	17:45:50	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.590	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE10	NAVI3
15/07/2023	18:55:20	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.267	Elevator	ASCE	At the bottom	MOM23ASCE11	NAVI3
15/07/2023	21:15:40	N 37 17.175	W 032 16.772	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV6	PL3
15/07/2023	22:52:50	N 37 17.373	W 032 16.508	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV8	
16/07/2023	00:45:40	N 37 17.371	W 032 16.509	VICTOR	ROV	Incident	MOM23ROV9	Black-out
16/07/2023	01:00:50	N 37 17.374	W 032 16.507	VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom	MOM23ROV10	Fin PL3
16/07/2023	04:00:10	N 37 17.587	W 032 15.678	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV11	
16/07/2023	11:11:00	N 37 16.959	W 032 16.527	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV12	PL4
16/07/2023	13:04:30	N 37 17.375	W 032 16.483	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV13	
16/07/2023	19:18:00			Elevator	ASCE	Release		NAVI3
16/07/2023	19:40:00			Elevator	ASCE	At the surface		
16/07/2023	20:02:00			Elevator	ASCE	Onboard		
16/07/2023	23:28:00			Elevator	ASCE	Mooring		NAVI4
17/07/2023	08:55:00	N 37 17.314	W 032 16.561	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE12	NAVI4
17/07/2023	09:15:00	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.607	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE13	
17/07/2023	09:25:30	N 37 17.295	W 032 16.522	Elevator	ASCE	Onboard	MOM23ASCE14	
17/07/2023	12:02:50	N 37 17.424	W 032 16.666	VICTOR	ROV	Incident	MOM23ROV14	Blackout
17/07/2023	12:04:20	N 37 17.424	W 032 16.666	VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom	MOM23ROV15	
17/07/2023	13:21:40	N 37 17.682	W 032 16.115	VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV16	
17/07/2023	14:00:10	N 37 18.254	W 032 15.915	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV17 -	Fin PL4
17/07/2023	15:11:00			Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release acoustique		LSVWP
17/07/2023	16:20:40	N 37 18.166	W 032 19.580	Autonomous OBS	OBS	At the surface	MOM23OBS6	LSVWP
17/07/2023	16:39:40	N 37 17.721	W 032 19.530	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS7	
17/07/2023	17:19:30	N 37 18.109	W 032 16.759	Mouillage océano	OCEANO	Release	MOM23OCEANO1:	
17/07/2023	17:32:40	N 37 18.094	W 032 16.713	Mouillage océano	OCEANO	At the surface	MOM23OCEANO2:	
17/07/2023	17:32:40			Mouillage océano	OCEANO	Filage	MOM23OCEANO2	
17/07/2023	20:00:00			Mouillage océano	OCEANO	Onboard	MOM23OCEANO2	
17/07/2023	20:44:10	N 37 17.948	W 032 19.544	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Mooring	MOM23OBS8	LSVWQ by Winch CTD cast
17/07/2023	22:22:20	N 37 17.932	W 032 19.534	Winch Bathy	OBS	Release	MOM23OBS9	
17/07/2023	23:15:30	N 37 18.138	W 032 19.360	Winch Bathy	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS10	
18/07/2023	03:06:10	N 37 15.924	W 032 18.022	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release acoustique	MOM23OBS11	LSVSP
18/07/2023	04:21:40	N 37 15.853	W 032 18.051	Autonomous OBS	OBS	At the surface	MOM23OBS12	
18/07/2023	04:50:10	N 37 15.692	W 032 17.806	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS13	
18/07/2023	05:27:40	N 37 15.628	W 032 17.865	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Mooring	MOM23OBS14	LSVWQ by Winch CTD cast
18/07/2023	07:46:40	N 37 15.618	W 032 17.860	Winch Bathy	OBS	Release	MOM23OBS16	Release OBS
18/07/2023	08:40:10	N 37 15.620	W 032 17.858	Winch Bathy	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS17	
18/07/2023	09:42:00			Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release acoustique		LSVNP
18/07/2023	11:10:20	N 37 19.059	W 032 17.068	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS19	
18/07/2023	11:35:10	N 37 19.150	W 032 16.852	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Mooring	MOM23OBS20	LSVWQ by Winch Bathy
18/07/2023	12:54:20	N 37 19.150	W 032 16.844	Winch Bathy	OBS	Release	MOM23OBS21	
18/07/2023	13:40:10	N 37 19.150	W 032 16.838	Winch Bathy	OBS	Onboard	MOM23OBS22	
18/07/2023	14:33:10	N 37 17.756	W 032 16.735	CTD cast	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY1	SEABIRD 19+
18/07/2023	14:53:50	N 37 17.756	W 032 16.735	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	At the bottom	MOM23BATHY2	At the bottom : 600 m from oceanographic mooring for intercalibration
18/07/2023	15:31:50	N 37 17.761	W 032 16.727	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Onboard	MOM23BATHY3	
18/07/2023	15:36:20	N 37 17.762	W 032 16.727	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY4	
18/07/2023	16:12:00	N 37 17.763	W 032 16.728	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	At the bottom	MOM23BATHY5	1600 m - point mouillage océano - pour intercalibration

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Nom abyeuil	Code instrum	Nom action	Identificateur Opération	Comment
18/07/2023	17:02:00	N 37 17.763	W 032 16.728	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Onboard	MOM23BATHY6	
18/07/2023	17:54:20	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.538	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY7	Tour Eiffel – plume experiment
18/07/2023	23:56:10	N 37 17.425	W 032 16.622	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Onboard	MOM23BATHY8	
19/07/2023	00:17:30	N 37 17.523	W 032 16.655	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE15	NAVI5
19/07/2023	00:40:00	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.651	Elevator	ASCE	At the bottom	MOM23ASCE16	NAVI5
19/07/2023	01:42:40	N 37 17.866	W 032 16.857	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV18	PL5
19/07/2023	02:44:10	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.714	VICTOR	ROV	Incident	MOM23ROV19	Blackout
19/07/2023	04:32:50	N 37 16.810	W 032 17.031	VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV20	
19/07/2023	05:11:10	N 37 16.678	W 032 16.362	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV21	Fin PL5
19/07/2023	10:45:00	N 37 17.356	W 032 16.562	CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY9	Mooring : Point 37°17,357'N 32°16,561'W
19/07/2023	16:50:00			CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	At the bottom	MOM23BATHY	
19/07/2023	21:38:00			CTD cast SEABIRD	BATHY	At the surface	MOM23BATHY	
19/07/2023	22:36:00			VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV	PL6
20/07/2023	07:00:00			Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE	NAVI5
20/07/2023	07:35:00			Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE	NAVI5
20/07/2023	17:30:00			Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE	NAVI6
20/07/2023	18:36:00			Elevator	ASCE	At the bottom	MOM23ASCE	NAVI6
21/07/2023	07:20:30	N 37 17.299	W 032 16.522	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE17	NAVI6
21/07/2023	08:04:10	N 37 17.227	W 032 16.333	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE18	NAVI6
21/07/2023	14:05:00	N 37 17.429	W 032 15.741	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE19	NAVI7
21/07/2023	14:39:30	N 37 17.429	W 032 15.887	Elevator	ASCE	At the bottom	MOM23ASCE20	NAVI7
21/07/2023	16:32:00	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.736	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE21	NAVI7
21/07/2023	16:46:30	N 37 17.385	W 032 15.795	Elevator	ASCE	Incident	MOM23ASCE22	
21/07/2023	17:21:00	N 37 17.383	W 032 15.919	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE23	NAVI7
22/07/2023	06:59:30	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.579	VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom	MOM23ROV22	Fin PL6
22/07/2023	08:10:00	N 37 17.018	W 032 16.894	VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV23	Fin PL6
22/07/2023	08:52:00	N 37 16.417	W 032 17.321	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV24	
22/07/2023	11:00:20	N 37 16.966	W 032 16.507	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Mooring	MOM23SEAMONE1	
22/07/2023	13:51:30	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.537	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Release	MOM23SEAMONE2	
22/07/2023	15:07:10	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.532	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONE3	
22/07/2023	17:04:40	N 37 17.371	W 032 16.476	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE24	NAVI8
22/07/2023	17:57:10	N 37 17.601	W 032 16.274	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV25	PL7
22/07/2023	19:41:50	N 37 17.306	W 032 16.451	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV26	PL7
23/07/2023	07:51:50	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.614	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Release	MOM23SEAMONE4	Displacement buoyancy
23/07/2023	08:22:10	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.647	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONE5	Displacement buoyancy
23/07/2023	08:26:30	N 37 17.312	W 032 16.647	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE25	NAVI8
23/07/2023	08:30:30	N 37 17.308	W 032 16.654	VICTOR	ROV	Débyt fond	MOM23ROV27	Fin PL7
23/07/2023	09:00:10	N 37 17.253	W 032 16.738	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE26	NAVI8
23/07/2023	09:15:10	N 37 17.152	W 032 16.677	Elevator	ASCE	Onboard	MOM23ASCE27	NAVI8
23/07/2023	09:35:40	N 37 17.138	W 032 16.559	VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV28	
23/07/2023	10:12:10	N 37 17.037	W 032 15.860	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV29	
23/07/2023	11:34:40	N 37 16.998	W 032 16.934	Câble grand fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Mooring	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE7	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
23/07/2023	15:15:00	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.539	Câble grand fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Release	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE8	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est
23/07/2023	16:10:30	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.539	Câble grand fond	FLOTTARECUPE	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE9:	Recovery buoyancy SEAMON Est :
23/07/2023	17:25:10	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.474	Elevator	ASCE	Mooring	MOM23ASCE28	NAVI9
23/07/2023	18:39:40	N 37 17.147	W 032 16.355	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV30	PL8
23/07/2023	20:04:10	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.573	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV31	
24/07/2023	07:02:40	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.468	Elevator	ASCE	Release	MOM23ASCE29	NAVI9
24/07/2023	07:06:10	N 37 17.294	W 032 16.472	VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom	MOM23ROV32	Fin PL8

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Nom abyeil	Code instrum	Nom action	Identificateur Opération	Comment
24/07/2023	07:37:30	N 37 17.084	W 032 16.616	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE30	NAVI9
24/07/2023	07:52:00	N 37 17.241	W 032 16.669	Elevator	ASCE	Onboard	MOM23ASCE31	NAVI9
24/07/2023	08:00:10	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.713	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE32	
24/07/2023	08:52:40	N 37 18.062	W 032 17.633	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV34	
24/07/2023	09:32:50	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.568	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	Release	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE11	Flotta + Station Est
24/07/2023	10:10:40	N 37 16.831	W 032 16.614	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	At the surface	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE10	
24/07/2023	11:32:20	N 37 17.731	W 032 16.494	SEAMON E	FLOTTARECUPE	Onboard	MOM23FLOTTARECUPE12	SEAMON E et Flottabilité à bord
24/07/2023	14:28:00	N 37 17.205	W 032 16.992	Câble grand fond	SEAMONW	Mooring	MOM23SEAMONW3	SEAMON W
24/07/2023	17:32:30	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.808	Câble grand fond	SEAMONW	Release	MOM23SEAMONW4:	SEAMON W
24/07/2023	17:39:20	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.808	Câble grand fond	SEAMONW	Virage	MOM23SEAMONW5	
24/07/2023	18:30:50	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.807	Câble grand fond	SEAMONW	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONW6	
24/07/2023	19:11:50	N 37 17.231	W 032 17.090	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV35	PL9
24/07/2023	20:35:20	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.835	Elevator	ASCE	At the bottom	MOM23ASCE33	PL9
25/07/2023	06:19:40	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.848	SEAMON W	SEAMONW	Release	MOM23SEAMONW7	Displacement buoyancy
25/07/2023	06:50:10	N 37 17.587	W 032 16.924	SEAMON W	SEAMONW	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONW8	Displacement buoyancy
25/07/2023	08:35:30	N 37 17.684	W 032 16.706	Elevator	ASCE	At the surface	MOM23ASCE34	Fin PL9
25/07/2023	09:12:10	N 37 18.395	W 032 16.471	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV36	
25/07/2023	10:23:30	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.527	CTD cast	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY10	
25/07/2023	14:40:50	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.529	CTD cast	BATHY	At the bottom	MOM23BATHY11	1660 m
25/07/2023	15:51:20	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.527	CTD cast	BATHY	At the surface	MOM23BATHY12	
25/07/2023	16:10:40	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.527	CTD cast	BATHY	Onboard	MOM23BATHY13	
25/07/2023	17:10:10	N 37 16.947	W 032 16.234	Câble grand fond	SEAMONE	Mooring	MOM23SEAMONE8	SEAMON E
25/07/2023	20:22:30	N 37 17.370	W 032 16.578	Câble grand fond	SEAMONE	Release	MOM23SEAMONE9	SEAMON E
25/07/2023	21:49:30	N 37 17.370	W 032 16.577	Câble grand fond	SEAMONE	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONE10	
25/07/2023	22:37:50	N 37 17.048	W 032 16.754	VICTOR	ROV	Mooring	MOM23ROV37	PL10
26/07/2023	00:15:30	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.567	VICTOR	ROV	At the bottom	MOM23ROV38	PL10
26/07/2023	07:28:10	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.492	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Release	MOM23SEAMONE11	Flottabilité de déplacement
26/07/2023	08:00:30	N 37 17.372	W 032 16.442	SEAMON E	SEAMONE	Onboard	MOM23SEAMONE12	Displacement buoyancy
26/07/2023	13:32:00	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.494	VICTOR	ROV	Incident	MOM23ROV39	Black-out
26/07/2023	13:43:30	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.480	VICTOR	ROV	Off the bottom	MOM23ROV40	Fin PL10
26/07/2023	15:15:00	N 37 17.772	W 032 16.770	VICTOR	ROV	At the surface	MOM23ROV41	
26/07/2023	15:57:30	N 37 17.314	W 032 16.454	VICTOR	ROV	Onboard	MOM23ROV42	
26/07/2023	17:04:10	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.540	CTD cast	BATHY	Mooring	MOM23BATHY14	Plume experiment
26/07/2023	23:10:40	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.528	CTD cast	BATHY	At the bottom	MOM23BATHY15	
27/07/2023	01:00:10	N 37 17.463	W 032 16.620	CTD cast	BATHY	Onboard	MOM23BATHY16	

7. Dive summaries

7.1. MoMARSAT 2023 Dive 839-1

July, 13th 2023

Victor launching position			
Launching position NAVI1	N37°17.3662	W 32°16.4729	
Buoyancy device target SEAMON W	N32°17.4810	W32°16.7699	
Launching time	07:20	Time of arrival at the bottom	09:01
Departure from bottom	06:05 le 14 juillet	Time Victor on board	07:50

7.1.1. Objectives

Seamon W storage and hooking, Seamon East & DEAFS storage + cable, probe exchanges, titanium sampling

Coordinates:

SEAMON W	N 37°17.486	W 32°16.755	1741	Mooring of the recovery buoyancy device SEAMON W
Coloniser ANA	N 37°17.465	W 32°16.790		3 Colonisers
SAEMON E	N 37°17.316	W 32°16.539		
Montsegur/DEAFS	N 37°17.283	W 32°16.542	1704	
HTW019	37°17.28218	32°116.53580'		Montsegur

Victor

Descending basket

4 Gaz tights	PBT1	Niskin	Longe TEMPO
Green basket for probes			Longe DEAFs

Ascending basket

4 Gaz tights	PBT2	Niskin	HTW019
Green basket for 8 probes			

Instrumentation

PEP	Suction sampler		
-----	-----------------	--	--

NAVI1

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 1	2 Quadrats DEEP-REST	DEAFS
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBT2	4 gaz tights + PBT1

7.1.2. Operations summary

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	09:07	Lucky strike	N 37 17.429	W 032 16.799	1728	At the bottom 10 mn ago
13/07/2023	09:09	Seamon W	N 37 17.467	W 032 16.791	1731	Arrival on SeaMon W
13/07/2023	09:15	Seamon W	N 37 17.470	W 032 16.788	1735	Niskin triggered in the basket
13/07/2023	09:17	Seamon W	N 37 17.477	W 032 16.774	1732	Rope is not tangled but the garbage disappeared
13/07/2023	09:19	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.785	1736	Storing OBS
13/07/2023	09:19	Seamon W	N 37 17.476	W 032 16.786	1737	In the axis at N183°
13/07/2023	09:21	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.787	1738	Inspection SeaMON W
13/07/2023	09:50	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.784	1738	OBS sécured with a grit bag

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	09:53	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.785	1738	Sling buoyancy freed
13/07/2023	10:06	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.788	1736	Hooked
13/07/2023	10:09	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.786	1738	Visual on Ana 3 Colonisers
13/07/2023	10:16	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.792	1738	Sampling basalt
13/07/2023	10:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.464	W 032 16.793	1733	Start transit to ASC
13/07/2023	10:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.558	1691	Cimendef?
13/07/2023	10:52	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.543	1694	Montségur
13/07/2023	11:01	Elevator	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.441	1680	Arrival atASC
13/07/2023	11:03	Elevator	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.433	1677	BASKET 2 open
13/07/2023	11:08	Elevator	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.437	1676	Opening BASKET 1 ASC
13/07/2023	11:10	Elevator	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.435	1677	Taking 2 quadrats
13/07/2023	11:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.439	1673	Towards Montsegur
13/07/2023	11:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.540	1697	Temporary drop of 2 quadrats
13/07/2023	11:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.548	1699	Opening PBT1
13/07/2023	11:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	1699	BIOLUCKY in PBT1
13/07/2023	11:44	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.546	1699	disconnecton DEAFS
13/07/2023	12:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.545	1699	Bell is clogged in metal deposits
13/07/2023	12:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.544	1699	tube broken, no alternative
13/07/2023	12:44	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.541	1696	Bell dropped in the ROV basket
13/07/2023	12:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.543	1699	Measurement of T°C New DEAFS
13/07/2023	12:50	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.542	1699	T°C 312°C
13/07/2023	12:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.542	1699	Gaz tight Ti1 M23FLU01
13/07/2023	13:00	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.541	1699	Gaz tight Ti2 M23FLU02
13/07/2023	13:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	1699	Gaz tight Ti3 M23FLU03
13/07/2023	13:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1699	Gaz tight Ti4 M23FLU04
13/07/2023	13:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.544	1699	Cable coiled around DEAFS
13/07/2023	13:22	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.543	1699	Grabbing DEAFS with Maestro
13/07/2023	13:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.543	1697	Transit ASC
13/07/2023	13:37	Elevator	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.436	1676	Arrival at ASC
13/07/2023	13:40	Elevator	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.430	1676	DEAFS in BASKET 1
13/07/2023	14:13	Elevator	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.433	1677	closing BASKET 1
13/07/2023	14:33	Elevator	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.436	1677	Exchanges gaz tights BASKET 2
13/07/2023	15:09	Elevator	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.435	1676	PBT1 in ASC BASKET2
13/07/2023	15:13	Elevator	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.436	1676	PBT2
13/07/2023	15:27	Elevator	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.436	1677	ASC BASKET 2 closed
13/07/2023	15:29	Elevator	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.437	1677	Leaving for Montsegur
13/07/2023	15:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.535	1696	At Montsegur
13/07/2023	15:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.536	1697	HTWN019 in place
13/07/2023	15:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1698	HTWN019 recovered
13/07/2023	15:58	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.537	1697	Debut Manip Ti
13/07/2023	16:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.542	1697	Measurement de la Temperature
13/07/2023	16:13	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.540	1697	315°C
13/07/2023	16:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.539	1697	Rangement de la probe T°
13/07/2023	16:47	Montsegur	N 37 17.158	W 032 16.594	1651	Elevator en surface
13/07/2023	17:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.212	W 032 16.726	1615	elevator à bord
13/07/2023	17:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.536	1698	Gaz tight Ti5 M23FLU05
13/07/2023	17:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.537	1698	Gaz tight Ti8 M23FLU06
13/07/2023	17:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.537	1698	Gaz tight Ti7 M23FLU07
13/07/2023	18:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.534	1693	Seamon EAsT
13/07/2023	18:22	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.535	1693	photo Seamon East
13/07/2023	18:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	storing TEMPO
13/07/2023	18:44	Seamon E	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.535	1693	TEMPO arms stored
13/07/2023	18:52	Seamon E	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1692	TEMPO stored
13/07/2023	19:00	Seamon E	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.536	1694	Second lock in place
13/07/2023	19:19	Seamon E	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.533	1694	Deconnection hydroctopus
13/07/2023	19:33	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.545	1694	Arrival at soleil
13/07/2023	19:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement T 1 on small mussels

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	19:50	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 1 T 8.5 max
13/07/2023	19:51	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement 2 in grey 8.5
13/07/2023	19:52	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement 3 in grey 5 cm deep max
13/07/2023	19:55	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	Measurement 3 up to 51.2
13/07/2023	19:56	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	Measurement 4 bacterial mat on red substrate 5.2
13/07/2023	19:58	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 5 orange substrate 10.86
13/07/2023	19:59	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 6 2 cm on orange substrate 13.4
13/07/2023	20:02	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 7 on hard substrate small mussels 5.2
13/07/2023	20:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 8 on grey substrate, small mussels and bacterial mats 8.9
13/07/2023	20:05	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 9 grey substrate, bacterial mats probe pushed to the deepest
13/07/2023	20:06	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 9 60.7
13/07/2023	20:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 10 white smooth substrate (barite?) 7.9
13/07/2023	20:09	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 11 probe deepen in smooth white substrate visible shimmering
13/07/2023	20:11	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 11 - 83.2
13/07/2023	20:12	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 12 on grey substrate within white crust 33.6
13/07/2023	20:14	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 13 on bacterial mat
13/07/2023	20:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 13 5.6
13/07/2023	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 14 on medium mussels with small
13/07/2023	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement
13/07/2023	20:17	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 14 5.25
13/07/2023	20:20	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 15 on orange substrate
13/07/2023	20:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 16 4.7
13/07/2023	20:22	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 17 less than 1 cm deep 6.98
13/07/2023	20:25	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 18 grey substrate 4.76
13/07/2023	20:26	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 19 about 5 cm deep? 15.5
13/07/2023	20:30	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 20 on weird thing
13/07/2023	20:32	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 20 on weird « sticks » 4.75
13/07/2023	20:35	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	Measurement 21 on grey substrate near LTmetal 13
13/07/2023	20:36	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 21 5.07
13/07/2023	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement
13/07/2023	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 22 8 cm deep at least
13/07/2023	20:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	Measurement 22 42.5
13/07/2023	20:45	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	LTmetal 13 recovered
13/07/2023	20:47	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	LTmetal 12 recovered
13/07/2023	20:51	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.540	1696	LTmetal14 recovered
13/07/2023	20:54	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.539	1696	LTgrad1 in iron mat recovered
13/07/2023	20:56	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	HTnke41003 recovered
13/07/2023	21:00	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	LTgrad9 recovered
13/07/2023	21:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	LTgrad13 installed
13/07/2023	21:07	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.543	1696	HTnke38001 recovered

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	21:24	Seamon E	N 37 17.302	W 032 16.535	1697	survey cable DEAFS
13/07/2023	21:47	Seamon E	N 37 17.315	W 032 16.537	1700	caillebotis grabbed
13/07/2023	21:52	Seamon E	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.534	1694	câble ramené à Hydroctopus
13/07/2023	22:57	Seamon E	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.534	1695	câble DEAFS étrangle et accroché aune élingue de Seamon East
13/07/2023	23:42	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.540	1690	Sampling mussels dans PBT2
14/07/2023	24:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.538	1690	1st grab of mussels
14/07/2023	24:10	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.540	1690	2nd grab of mussels
14/07/2023	24:16	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.541	1690	3ème grab
14/07/2023	24:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.547	1690	4th grab
14/07/2023	24:29	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.544	1690	PBT2 closed
14/07/2023	24:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.539	1700	HTnke29016 recovered
14/07/2023	01:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.527	1700	HTnke41002 recovered
14/07/2023	01:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.527	1700	Suction sampler 2 –gastropods
14/07/2023	01:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	Suction sampler 3
14/07/2023	02:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.291	W 032 16.531	1698	quadrats montsegur
14/07/2023	02:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.531	1699	3 quadrats/POMME
14/07/2023	02:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.530	1700	temperature with PEP C1a
14/07/2023	02:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1700	start pep 3 C1a (sea water temp)
14/07/2023	02:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.531	1700	C1a temperature 4.87 max
14/07/2023	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	C2bcg tempertature center
14/07/2023	02:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.531	1700	C2bcg temperature 3th point
14/07/2023	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.528	1700	R0a Temperature 6.30
14/07/2023	03:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1700	C1bcg temperature 4.72
14/07/2023	03:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.530	1700	C1bcg Temperature in the midle (flux) 9.9
14/07/2023	03:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.533	1700	C1bcg juveniles mussels_ temp 6.41
14/07/2023	03:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.534	1699	C1a temperature 4.95
14/07/2023	03:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.532	1699	C1a measurement center
14/07/2023	03:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.534	1699	C1a edge temperature 5.47
14/07/2023	04:02	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1698	C2b temperature 5.13
14/07/2023	04:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.531	1698	C2b temperature 5.03
14/07/2023	04:06	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.527	1698	4.90 C2b mussels temp_
14/07/2023	04:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.530	1698	C2acg temperature 5.02
14/07/2023	04:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1698	C2acg center with crab temperature 5.19
14/07/2023	04:18	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.533	1698	small mussels temp 5.83
14/07/2023	04:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.529	1698	Mussels juveniles temp 5.28
14/07/2023	04:25	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.524	1698	C2acg 4.99
14/07/2023	04:26	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.526	1698	mussels 4.91
14/07/2023	04:27	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.528	1698	5.22
14/07/2023	04:29	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.530	1698	C2acg 4.90
14/07/2023	04:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1699	R1 Temperature 5.02
14/07/2023	04:51	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1699	R1 temperature center 5.10
14/07/2023	05:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.547	1691	Grouping the TCM D and B
14/07/2023	05:52	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.528	1691	TCM3-C grabbed
14/07/2023	06:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.548	1690	Retour sur TCM B et D
14/07/2023	06:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.546	1692	Déinstalling TCM C avec B et D
14/07/2023	06:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.545	1692	TCM B C et D

7.1.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	10:06	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.788	1736	Crochetage effectué
13/07/2023	11:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	1699	BIOLUCKY dans PBT1
13/07/2023	11:44	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.546	1699	déconnecton DEAFS

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	15:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1698	HTWN019 recovered
13/07/2023	18:52	Seamon Est	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1692	TEMPO
13/07/2023	20:45	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	LTmetal 13 recovered
13/07/2023	20:47	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	LTmetal 12 recovered
13/07/2023	20:51	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.540	1696	LTmetal14 recovered
13/07/2023	20:54	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.539	1696	LTgrad1 recovered
13/07/2023	20:56	Seamon Est	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	HTnke41003 recovered
13/07/2023	21:00	Seamon Est	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	LTgrad9 recovered
13/07/2023	21:04	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	LTgrad13 installed
13/07/2023	21:07	Seamon Est	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.543	1696	HTnke38001 recovered
14/07/2023	24:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.539	1700	HTnke29016 recovered
14/07/2023	01:17	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.527	1700	HTnke41002 recovered

7.1.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	09:15	Seamon W	N 37 17.470	W 032 16.788	1735	Triggering Niskin
13/07/2023	10:16	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.792	1738	Basalt grab
13/07/2023	12:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.542	1699	Gaz tight Ti1 M23FLU01
13/07/2023	13:00	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.541	1699	Gaz tight Ti2 M23FLU02
13/07/2023	13:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	1699	Gaz tight Ti3 M23FLU03
13/07/2023	13:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1699	Gaz tight Ti4 M23FLU04
13/07/2023	17:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.536	1698	Gaz tight Ti5 M23FLU05
13/07/2023	17:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.537	1698	Gaz tight Ti8 M23FLU06
13/07/2023	17:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.537	1698	Gaz tight Ti7 M23FLU07
13/07/2023	23:42	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.540	1690	Mussels in PBT2
						Suction sampler 1
14/07/2023	01:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.527	1700	Suction sampler 2, gastropods
14/07/2023	01:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	Suction sampler 3, gastropods
14/07/2023	02:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1700	start pep 3 (sea water temp)

7.1.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
13/07/2023	12:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.543	1699	Measurement of T°C New DEAFS – 312°C
13/07/2023	16:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.542	1697	Measurement of Temperature – 315°C
13/07/2023	19:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement T 1 on small mussels
13/07/2023	19:50	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 1 T 8.5 max
13/07/2023	19:51	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement 2 in grey 8.5
13/07/2023	19:52	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.543	1696	Measurement 3 in grey 5 cm deep max
13/07/2023	19:55	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	Measurement 3 up to 51.2
13/07/2023	19:56	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	Measurement 4 bacterial mat on red substrate 5.2
13/07/2023	19:58	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 5 orange substrate 10.86
13/07/2023	19:59	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 6 2 cm on orange substrate 13.4
13/07/2023	20:02	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 7 on hard substrate small mussels 5.2
13/07/2023	20:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 8 on grey substrate, small mussels and bacterial mats 8.9
13/07/2023	20:05	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 9 grey substrate, bacterial mats probe pushed to the deepest

13/07/2023	20:06	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 9 60.7
13/07/2023	20:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 10 white smooth substrate (barite?) 7.9
13/07/2023	20:09	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 11 probe deepen in smooth white substrate visible shimmering
13/07/2023	20:11	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 11 - 83.2
13/07/2023	20:12	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 12 on grey substrate within white crust 33.6
13/07/2023	20:14	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 13 on bacterial mat
13/07/2023	20:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 13 5.6
13/07/2023	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 14 on medium mussels with small
13/07/2023	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement
13/07/2023	20:17	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 14 5.25
13/07/2023	20:20	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 15 on orange substrate
13/07/2023	20:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 16 4.7
13/07/2023	20:22	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	Measurement 17 less than 1 cm deep 6.98
13/07/2023	20:25	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 18 grey substrate 4.76
13/07/2023	20:26	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 19 about 5 cm deep? 15.5
13/07/2023	20:30	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 20 on weird thing
13/07/2023	20:32	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 20 on weird « sticks » 4.75
13/07/2023	20:35	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	Measurement 21 on grey substrate near LTmetal 13
13/07/2023	20:36	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 21 5.07
13/07/2023	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement
13/07/2023	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	Measurement 22 8 cm deep at least
13/07/2023	20:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	Measurement 22 42.5
14/07/2023	02:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.531	1700	C1a temperature 4.87 max
14/07/2023	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	C2bcg tempertature center
14/07/2023	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.528	1700	R0a Temperature 6.30
14/07/2023	03:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1700	C1bcg temperature 4.72
14/07/2023	03:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.534	1699	C1a temperature 4.95
14/07/2023	04:02	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1698	C2b temperature 5.13
14/07/2023	04:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.530	1698	C2acg temperature 5.02
14/07/2023	04:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1699	R1 Temperature 5.02

7.1.6. Navigation

7.2. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 840-2

July 14th, Friday

Victor launching position	N37°17.3407	W 32°16,4392	
Launching position NAVI2	N37°17.3662	W 32°16.4729	
Position Flotta récup Seamon Est	N37°17.319	W 32°16.556	effective
Launching time	19h31	Time of arrival at the bottom	
Departure from bottom	05h58 le 15 juillet	Time Victor on board	07h58

7.2.1. Objectives

Hooking SEAMON Est, current meters recovery, MERCES, growth, probes and gaz tights

Coordinates :

Tour Eiffel	N 37°17.306	W 32°16.539	1705 m	
TCM3-C	N 37°17.343	W 32°16.526	1695 m	
TCM3-A (trou)	N 37°17.349	W 32°16.535	1704 m	
TCM3-D	N 37°17.349	W 32°16.5344		

Victor

Descending basket

4 Gaz tights		Samll BASKET with probes Mathilde	
PBT1	Niskin		

Ascending basket

4 Gaz tights		Small BASKET with probe Mathildes	
PBT2			

Instrumentation

Suction sampler	PEP		
-----------------	-----	--	--

NAVI2

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 1	4 gaz tights + PBT2	4 gaz tights + Niskin
BASKET 2	2 bells COMBO	PBT1 + 2 current meters

7.2.2 Operations summary

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
14/07/2023	20:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17.408	W 032 16.591	936	PEP 4 triggered
14/07/2023	20:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.409	W 032 16.587	958	PEP 5 triggered
14/07/2023	20:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.411	W 032 16.580	990	PEP6 triggered
14/07/2023	20:36	Lucky strike	N 37 17.413	W 032 16.573	1012	PEP7 triggered
14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.564	1037	PEP8 triggered
14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.559	1060	PEP9 triggered
14/07/2023	20:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.417	W 032 16.556	1082	PEP10 triggered
14/07/2023	21:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17.382	W 032 16.461	1624	start recordings
14/07/2023	21:02	Lucky strike	N 37 17.384	W 032 16.460	1652	ROV At the bottom
14/07/2023	21:10	Lucky strike	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.524	1690	Arrival elevator
14/07/2023	21:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.534	1688	opening BASKET 1
14/07/2023	21:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.536	1688	opening BASKET 2
14/07/2023	21:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1691	Niskin triggered
14/07/2023	21:26	Seamon E	N 37 17.317	W 032 16.542	1679	Visual on buoyancy device
14/07/2023	21:42	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.531	1690	Seamon E, cable DEAFS

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
14/07/2023	21:44	Lucky strike	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.528	1687	Star transit towards Aisics
14/07/2023	21:54	Aisics	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.533	1688	recovery HTWN021
14/07/2023	22:08	Aisics	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1688	grab de T°C 305°C
14/07/2023	22:18	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.534	1688	Ti5 M23FLU08
14/07/2023	22:22	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti6 M23FLU09
14/07/2023	22:26	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.532	1688	Ti7 M23FLU10
14/07/2023	22:30	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti8 M23FLU11
14/07/2023	22:49	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	installing HTWN19
14/07/2023	23:00	Aisics	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.529	1688	grab LSTE9
14/07/2023	23:04	Aisics	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.529	1688	LSTE9 stored in PBT1
14/07/2023	23:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.534	1684	TCM3_A found
14/07/2023	23:43	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.540	1689	Arrival storage area TCM
14/07/2023	23:46	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.540	1692	recovery du TCM3_C
14/07/2023	23:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.541	1692	recovery TCM3_B
15/07/2023	24:27	Elevator	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.536	1690	Manip elevator
15/07/2023	24:35	Elevator	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.536	1689	TCM3-C dans ASC BASKET 2
15/07/2023	24:37	Elevator	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.535	1689	TCM3-B dans l'ASC BASKET 2
15/07/2023	24:46	Elevator	N 37 17.317	W 032 16.531	1689	startechanges gaz tights
15/07/2023	01:41	Elevator	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.532	1689	fini manip elevator
15/07/2023	01:54	Soleil	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.546	1695	Arrival sur soleil
15/07/2023	02:12	Soleil	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.540	1696	Installing HTNKE30001
15/07/2023	02:25	Soleil	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.540	1694	HTNKE 30002 recovered
15/07/2023	02:50	Soleil	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.540	1694	HTNKE29008 installed
15/07/2023	02:54	Soleil	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.541	1693	LTW017 recovered
15/07/2023	03:01	Soleil	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.545	1695	LTW003 recovered
15/07/2023	03:05	Soleil	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.546	1694	LTgrad2 recovered
15/07/2023	03:17	Soleil	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.546	1694	LTgrad15 installed
15/07/2023	03:25	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1693	HTNKE38003 recovered
15/07/2023	03:27	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.546	1693	LTgrad10 recovered
15/07/2023	03:39	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.535	1693	LTgrad9 installed
15/07/2023	03:52	Soleil	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.533	1688	HTNKE29020 recovered
15/07/2023	03:58	Soleil	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.533	1688	HTNKE30015 installed
15/07/2023	04:12	Soleil	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.528	1689	LTgrad1 installed
15/07/2023	04:14	Soleil	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.531	1689	LTgrad6 recovered
15/07/2023	04:18	Lucky strike	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.505	1688	TCM3- ? recovered
15/07/2023	04:31	Lucky strike	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.604	1683	transit towards Isabel
15/07/2023	04:35	Isabel	N 37 17.386	W 032 16.628	1681	Arrival towards Isabel
15/07/2023	04:37	Isabel	N 37 17.396	W 032 16.636	1677	Fish
15/07/2023	04:49	Isabel	N 37 17.396	W 032 16.636	1677	T°C at 293°C
15/07/2023	04:55	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.639	1677	T°C at 296°C
15/07/2023	05:03	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti1 M23FLU12
15/07/2023	05:12	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti2 M23FLU13
15/07/2023	05:19	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Ti3 M23FLU14
15/07/2023	05:25	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.640	1677	End syringes
15/07/2023	05:35	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1676	Suction sampler jar 1
15/07/2023	05:38	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 2
15/07/2023	05:39	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 3
15/07/2023	05:40	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 4

7.2.3 Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
14/07/2023	21:42	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.531	1690	Seamon E, cable DEAFS
14/07/2023	21:54	Aisics	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.533	1688	recovery HTWN021
14/07/2023	22:49	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	installing HTWN19
14/07/2023	23:04	Aisics	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.529	1688	LSTE9 stored in PBT1
14/07/2023	23:46	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.540	1692	recovery TCM3_C

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
14/07/2023	23:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.541	1692	recovery TCM3_B
15/07/2023	02:12	Soleil	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.540	1696	Installing HTNKE30001
15/07/2023	02:25	Soleil	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.540	1694	HTNKE 30002 recovered
15/07/2023	02:50	Soleil	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.540	1694	HTNKE29008 installed
15/07/2023	02:54	Soleil	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.541	1693	LTW017 recovered
15/07/2023	03:01	Soleil	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.545	1695	LTW003 recovered
15/07/2023	03:05	Soleil	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.546	1694	LTgrad2 recovered
15/07/2023	03:17	Soleil	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.546	1694	LTgrad15 installed
15/07/2023	03:25	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1693	HTNKE38003 recovered
15/07/2023	03:27	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.546	1693	LTgrad10 recovered
15/07/2023	03:39	Soleil	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.535	1693	LTgrad9 installed
15/07/2023	03:52	Soleil	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.533	1688	HTNKE29020 recovered
15/07/2023	03:58	Soleil	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.533	1688	HTNKE30015 installed
15/07/2023	04:12	Soleil	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.528	1689	LTgrad1 installed
15/07/2023	04:14	Soleil	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.531	1689	LTgrad6 recovered
15/07/2023	04:18	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.505	1688	TCM3-D recovered

7.2.4 Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
14/07/2023	20:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17.408	W 032 16.591	936	PEP 4 triggered
14/07/2023	20:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.409	W 032 16.587	958	PEP 5 triggered
14/07/2023	20:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.411	W 032 16.580	990	PEP6 triggered
14/07/2023	20:36	Lucky strike	N 37 17.413	W 032 16.573	1012	PEP7 triggered
14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.564	1037	PEP8 triggered
14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.559	1060	PEP9 triggered
14/07/2023	20:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.417	W 032 16.556	1082	PEP10 triggered
14/07/2023	21:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1691	Déclenchement Niskin
14/07/2023	22:18	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.534	1688	Ti5 M23FLU08
14/07/2023	22:22	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti6 M23FLU09
14/07/2023	22:26	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.532	1688	Ti7 M23FLU10
14/07/2023	22:30	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti8 M23FLU11
15/07/2023	05:03	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti1 M23FLU12
15/07/2023	05:12	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti2 M23FLU13
15/07/2023	05:19	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Ti3 M23FLU14
15/07/2023	05:35	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1676	Suction sampler jar 1
15/07/2023	05:38	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 2
15/07/2023	05:39	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 3
15/07/2023	05:40	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction sampler jar 4

7.2.5 Measurements

14/07/2023	22:08	Aisics	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1688	T°C 305°C
15/07/2023	04:49	Isabel	N 37 17.396	W 032 16.636	1677	T à 293°C

7.2.6 Navigation

7.3 MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 841-3

July 15th, Saturday, 2023

Launching position Victor	N 37 17.3181	W 032 16.5016	
Launching NAVI3	N 37°17.3692	W 32° 16.4402	
Launching time	21:15	Time of arrival at the bottom	22:52
Departure from bottom	01:00 on July 16	Time Victor on board	04:00

7.3.1. Objectives

Recovery of autonomous sensors East sites, MERCES, growth, exchanges probes in the west

Coordinates :

Montsegur				
TCM3-2	N 37°17.304	W 32°16.532	1705 m	Tour Eiffel
TCM3-D	N 37°17.350	W 32°16.534	1693 m	Tour Eiffel
TCM3-1				

Victor

Descending basket

PBT2 (avec cage G12/G24)	4 Gaz tights bells	4 Probes in small BASKET	
PBT1 (LSNTE1)	PBT3 (avec cage M12/M24)	1 small probe	1 probe HTWN

Ascending basket

PBT1	4 Titane bells	Probes	
PBT2	PBT3	HTW	

NAVI3

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBTs 4 et 5	4 gaz tights bells + 2 PBT
BASKET 1	SPIDER)	TCM3-2 et TCM3-D + 1 PBT

7.3.2 Operations summary

Incident ROV

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
15/07/2023	22:54	Lucky strike	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.517	1692	Victor At the bottom.
15/07/2023	23:03	Lucky strike	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.496	1693	Transit towards Tour Eiffel Nord
15/07/2023	23:11	TE Nord	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.532	1687	Arrival satTE nord
15/07/2023	23:16	TE Nord	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.537	1690	T° 55°C
15/07/2023	23:28	TE Nord	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.538	1690	Ti1 M23FLU15
15/07/2023	23:35	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.541	1690	Ti2 M23FLU16
15/07/2023	23:41	TE Nord	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.536	1690	Ti3 M23FLU17
15/07/2023	23:45	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.540	1690	Ti4 M23FLU18
16/07/2023	24:05	TE Nord	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.540	1690	deployment lsnte1
16/07/2023	24:14	TE Nord	N 37 17.353	W 032 16.541	1686	Arrival on iron mat
16/07/2023	24:22	TE Nord	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.544	1689	Measurement of temperature on iron mat
16/07/2023	24:24	TE Nord	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.542	1689	Sampling pep bag 1 3mn
16/07/2023	24:43	TE Nord	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.540	1689	abandon mission 3.9l huile

7.3.3 Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	24:05	TE Nord	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.540	1690	deployment lsnte1

7.3.4 Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
15/07/2023	23:28	TE Nord	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.538	1690	Ti1 M23FLU15
15/07/2023	23:35	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.541	1690	Ti2 M23FLU16
15/07/2023	23:41	TE Nord	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.536	1690	Ti3 M23FLU17
15/07/2023	23:45	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.540	1690	Ti4 M23FLU18

7.3.5 Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
15/07/2023	23:16	TE Nord	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.537	1690	T° measured 55°C
16/07/2023	24:22	TE Nord	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.544	1689	Measurement temperature on iron mat

7.3.6 Navigation

7.4. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 842-4

July 15th, Saturday

Launching position Victor	N 37 17.3181	W 032 16.5016	
Launching NAVI4	N 37°17.3692	W 32° 16.4402	
Launching time	11h11	Time of arrival at the bottom	13h04
Departure from bottom	12h04 le 17 juillet	Time Victor on board	14h00

7.4.1. Objectives

Recovery probes of temperature White Castle, South Crystal, Cyprès

INCIDENT ROV end of dive – emergency recovery

Coordinates :

South Crystal	37°17.43531	32°16.93107	1724
Cyprès	37°17.43915	32°16.86419	1742
White Castle	37°17.38747	32°16.863879	1710

Configuration Victor :

NAVI3 (déjà At the bottom)

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBTs 4 et 5	4 gaz tights bells + 2 PBT
BASKET 1 (plancher bas)	SPIDER	TCM3-2 et TCM3-D + 1 PBT

NAVI4

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights bells + PBT1(LSY31), PBT2 (G36) et PBT3 (M36)	4 gaz tights + 2 HTWN
BASKET 1 (plancher bas)	2 COMBOs	TCM3-1 + PBT4 et PBT5

Instrumentation

PEP (4 bags de 15 à 18)	Suction sampler	
-------------------------	-----------------	--

7.4.2. Operations summary:

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	13:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.509	1700	Arrival at the bottom at Hydro4
16/07/2023	13:09	Nord TE	N 37 17.355	W 032 16.506	1691	Towards iron mat at Nord TE
16/07/2023	13:27	Nord TE	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.523	1689	Measurement Temperature 4,65°C
16/07/2023	13:28	Nord TE	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.528	1689	Sampling Bag PEP 16 NTE Filtered
16/07/2023	13:31	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.538	1689	Fin sampling Bag PEP 16
16/07/2023	13:32	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.539	1690	Sampling Bag PEP 17 NTE Non filtered
16/07/2023	13:35	Nord TE	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.538	1689	Fin sampling Bag PEP 17
16/07/2023	13:49	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.533	1690	Sampling Mat FeOx-NTE
16/07/2023	13:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.353	W 032 16.531	1687	Transit towards Montsegur
16/07/2023	14:07	Montsegur	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.530	1696	Arrival Montségur
16/07/2023	14:42	Montsegur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.537	1699	Measurement T° = 315°C
16/07/2023	14:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti1 M23FLU19
16/07/2023	15:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.534	1699	Ti2 M23FLU20
16/07/2023	15:07	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Broken inlet, Gaz tight in hole, Ti3 M23FLU21
16/07/2023	15:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti4 M23FLU22
16/07/2023	15:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.533	1701	Cage G12/G24 deployed
16/07/2023	16:00	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.530	1701	PEP 1 in the center of the C2a temp
16/07/2023	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.530	1701	C2a temp: 4.60 - 4.76
16/07/2023	16:02	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.530	1701	PEP 2 C2a temp- 4.60
16/07/2023	16:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.530	1701	sampling C2a in PBT2
16/07/2023	16:27	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.531	1701	Suction sampler 1 & 2 in C2a
16/07/2023	16:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1701	Moving POMME 3 in C1b
16/07/2023	16:39	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.529	1700	POMME 3 in storage

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	16:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.530	1700	Cage M12/M24 from PBT3 in the storagee area
16/07/2023	17:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.530	1701	C1b temperature top left 4.85
16/07/2023	17:07	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.529	1701	pep 4 on C1B
16/07/2023	17:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.529	1701	temp 8.19
16/07/2023	17:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.527	1701	sampling C1b in PBT3
16/07/2023	17:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1701	Suction sampler 3 bacterial mats C1b
16/07/2023	17:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.545	1693	Recovery of TCM3-3 & TCM3-D in storage area
16/07/2023	18:00	Elevator	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.495	1696	Arrival at ascenceur
16/07/2023	19:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.113	W 032 16.639	1619	Transit towards Tour Eiffel
16/07/2023	20:31	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.544	1692	Deployment quadrat, SPIDER experiment
16/07/2023	20:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Measurement T°C 5.55°C-5.67
16/07/2023	20:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.543	1693	PEP 5, T°C 4.70°C, 5.65°C. not working
16/07/2023	20:48	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.541	1693	PEP 6, T°C 5.62°C. slow pumping
16/07/2023	20:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Sulphide exposure
16/07/2023	21:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.543	1694	Cage M12/M24 in place
16/07/2023	21:06	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.543	1693	Towards Montségur
16/07/2023	21:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.541	1700	Sampling fauna at quadrat C1a
16/07/2023	21:16	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.540	1700	First grab PBT4
16/07/2023	21:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.539	1700	Probe PEP in place C1a 4.89°C, 4.96°C
16/07/2023	21:25	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.539	1700	Start PEP 7, manual pumping 100 seconds 4.81°C-4.90°C, 5.05°C
16/07/2023	21:29	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.541	1700	Start PEP 8, manual pumping 100 seconds, 4.89°C-5.°C
16/07/2023	21:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.539	1700	Fin PEP 7 et 8 sur quadrat C1a
16/07/2023	21:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction sampler4 sur quadrat C1a
16/07/2023	21:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Fin Suction sampler 4, start Suction sampler 5
16/07/2023	21:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.534	1699	Quadrat C2b
16/07/2023	21:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1699	PEP 9, T°C 4.70°C-4.74. manual pumping 100 seconds
16/07/2023	21:59	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.532	1699	PEP 10 sur Quadrat C2b. manual pumping 100 seconds 4.86-4.97°C
16/07/2023	22:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1699	Sampling pince faune quadrat C2b dans PBT5.
16/07/2023	22:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1700	Start Suction sampler 6 sur quadrat C2b
16/07/2023	22:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1700	Start Suction sampler 7 sur quadrat C2b
16/07/2023	22:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.541	1701	TCM3-1 recovered
16/07/2023	22:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.525	1692	Arrival hydroctopus. Black out.
16/07/2023	22:45	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.525	1690	End of blackout
16/07/2023	22:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.533	1697	Inspection of connection and hydrophone at hydroctopus
16/07/2023	22:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.527	1698	Towards hydro 4
16/07/2023	23:08	Lucky strike	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.509	1699	Hydro 4 seems globally OK , leakages but no big corrosion
16/07/2023	23:12	Lucky strike	N 37 17.315	W 032 16.545	1697	towards Hydro 2
16/07/2023	23:17	Lucky strike	N 37 17.311	W 032 16.580	1695	Few leakages but hydro2 is in good condition
16/07/2023	23:28	Lucky strike	N 37 17.312	W 032 16.581	1694	elevator released
16/07/2023	23:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.312	W 032 16.578	1693	Start transit ROV towards South Crystal
17/07/2023	24:09	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.938	1717	Arrival at South Crystal
17/07/2023	24:11	South Crystal	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.935	1718	snowman
17/07/2023	24:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.936	1719	Measurement T° = 324°C
17/07/2023	01:00	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.933	1719	Ti8 M23FLU23
17/07/2023	01:06	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti7 M23FLU24
17/07/2023	01:11	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti6 M23FLU25
17/07/2023	01:22	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.935	1719	Ti5 M23FLU26
17/07/2023	01:35	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.931	1720	HTNKE 30011 recovered
17/07/2023	01:50	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.932	1720	LTW03 installed
17/07/2023	01:54	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	1720	LTW06 recovered
17/07/2023	02:18	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	1720	LTW18 installed
17/07/2023	02:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.932	1720	Départ towards White Castle
17/07/2023	03:10	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.868	1709	HTW005 recovered
17/07/2023	04:23	White Castle	N 37 17.392	W 032 16.863	1721	HTWN013 recovered
17/07/2023	04:28	White Castle	N 37 17.391	W 032 16.863	1721	HTNKE29017 recovered
17/07/2023	04:35	White Castle	N 37 17.393	W 032 16.862	1721	HTWN021 installed

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
17/07/2023	04:42	White Castle	N 37 17.387	W 032 16.870	1712	HTNKE30012 recovered
17/07/2023	04:53	White Castle	N 37 17.388	W 032 16.869	1712	HTNKE30002 installed
17/07/2023	05:06	White Castle	N 37 17.401	W 032 16.867	1720	LTgrad8 recovered
17/07/2023	05:20	White Castle	N 37 17.402	W 032 16.867	1720	LTgrad5 installed
17/07/2023	05:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.538	1692	Arrival at Hydroctopus
17/07/2023	05:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.528	1700	Recovery TCM3-1
17/07/2023	05:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.528	1700	Transit towards elevator.
17/07/2023	06:00	Elevator	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.432	1658	Elevator
17/07/2023	06:58	Elevator	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.429	1658	End elevator
17/07/2023	07:03	Lucky strike	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.430	1669	Direction Tour Eiffel with 2 Combos
17/07/2023	07:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.538	1687	Combo 2 triggered
17/07/2023	07:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.537	1687	Combo 1 installed
17/07/2023	07:46	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.527	1685	Change: start Spider experiment
17/07/2023	08:03	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.545	1693	Grab temperature probe 4 5.87
17/07/2023	08:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.543	1692	5.85°C-5.94
17/07/2023	08:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	PEP 11, T°C 5.40°C
17/07/2023	08:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.543	1693	PEP 11 at the center of experimental quadrat SPIDER
17/07/2023	08:08	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.543	1693	Start PEP 12, 5.67°C, 80 secondes
17/07/2023	08:09	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.543	1693	Stop PEP 12
17/07/2023	08:10	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.543	1693	T°C small mussels 5.10°C_5.02-5.
17/07/2023	08:15	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.541	1693	Sampling mussels sulfure zone PBT2
17/07/2023	08:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Suction sampler, jar 8
17/07/2023	08:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Transit Montségur
17/07/2023	08:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.294	W 032 16.537	1698	Storage area
17/07/2023	08:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.533	1701	POMME 2sur R0
17/07/2023	08:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.533	1701	T°C bottom R0a, 11.80°C, 13.76, 15.73
17/07/2023	08:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.533	1701	PEP 13 on quadrat R0a, TC 14.08, 13.44
17/07/2023	08:43	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1701	Start PEP 14 on quadrat R0a, 13.35, 14.27, 12.80
17/07/2023	08:51	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1701	End quadrat R0a
17/07/2023	08:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1701	Drop POMME2 in storage area
17/07/2023	08:54	Lucky strike	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.537	1698	Elevator released, 1000 m
17/07/2023	09:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.549	1693	Tour Eiffel SPIDER area & cage M12/M24
17/07/2023	09:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.550	1693	Opening PBT3 with cage M36
17/07/2023	09:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.547	1693	Cage M36 installed
17/07/2023	09:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.546	1693	Start sampling big mussels in PBT3
17/07/2023	09:32	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.545	1690	Ruler – start plume experiment
17/07/2023	10:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.531	1683	End Experiment FLUX.
17/07/2023	10:28	Lucky strike	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.583	1682	Transit towards Y3.
17/07/2023	11:00	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.667	1727	Working area on mats FeOx Y3
17/07/2023	11:01	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.669	1728	Grab probe temperature ROV
17/07/2023	11:12	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	M23-FLU27 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:22	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.670	1728	Sampling M23-FLU28 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:27	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	Sampling M23-FLU29 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:32	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.666	1728	Sampling M23-FLU30 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:45	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.670	1728	Deployment Coloniser LSY3-1
17/07/2023	12:00	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.668	1728	Sampling PEP 18 Bag filtered 3 min
17/07/2023	12:02	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.668	-100	Black out
17/07/2023	12:05	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.668	-100	Stop Videos

7.4.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	15:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.533	1701	Cage G12/G24 deployed
16/07/2023	17:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.545	1693	Recovery TCM3-3 & TCM3-D dans la storage area
16/07/2023	21:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.543	1694	Cage mussels M12/M24 in place
16/07/2023	22:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.541	1701	TCM3-1 recovered
17/07/2023	01:35	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.931	1720	HTNKE 30011 recovered
17/07/2023	01:50	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.932	1720	LTW03 installed
17/07/2023	01:54	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	1720	LTW06 recovered
17/07/2023	02:18	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	1720	LTW18 installed
17/07/2023	03:10	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.868	1709	HTW005 recovered
17/07/2023	04:23	White Castle	N 37 17.392	W 032 16.863	1721	HTWN013 recovered
17/07/2023	04:28	White Castle	N 37 17.391	W 032 16.863	1721	HTNKE29017 recovered
17/07/2023	04:35	White Castle	N 37 17.393	W 032 16.862	1721	HTWN021 installed
17/07/2023	04:42	White Castle	N 37 17.387	W 032 16.870	1712	HTNKE30012 recovered
17/07/2023	04:53	White Castle	N 37 17.388	W 032 16.869	1712	HTNKE30002 installed
17/07/2023	05:06	White Castle	N 37 17.401	W 032 16.867	1720	LTgrad8 recovered
17/07/2023	05:20	White Castle	N 37 17.402	W 032 16.867	1720	LTgrad5 installed
17/07/2023	07:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.538	1687	Combo 2 installed
17/07/2023	07:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.537	1687	Combo 1 installed
17/07/2023	09:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.547	1693	Cage M36 installed
17/07/2023	11:45	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.670	1728	Deployment Coloniser LSY3-1

7.4.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	13:28	Nord TE	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.528	1689	Sampling Bag PEP 16 NTE Filtered
16/07/2023	13:32	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.539	1690	Sampling Bag PEP 17 NTE Non filtered
16/07/2023	13:49	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.533	1690	Sampling Mat M23FeOx-NTE PBT1
16/07/2023	14:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti1 M23FLU19
16/07/2023	15:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.534	1699	Ti2 M23FLU20
16/07/2023	15:08	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.534	1699	Ti2 M23FLU21
16/07/2023	15:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti4 M23FLU22
16/07/2023	16:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.530	1701	sampling C2a in PBT2
16/07/2023	16:27	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.531	1701	Suction sampler 1 & 2 in C2a
16/07/2023	17:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.527	1701	sampling C1b in PBT3
16/07/2023	17:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1701	Suction sampler 3 bacterial mats C1b
16/07/2023	21:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.541	1700	Sampling fauna on quadrat C1a in PBT4
16/07/2023	21:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction sampler4 on quadrat C1a
16/07/2023	21:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction sampler 5 on quadrat C1a
16/07/2023	22:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1699	Sampling fauna quadrat C2b in PBT5.
16/07/2023	22:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1700	StartSuction sampler 6 on quadrat C2b
16/07/2023	22:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1700	Déubt Suction sampler 7 on quadrat C2b
17/07/2023	01:00	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.933	1719	Ti8 M23FLU23
17/07/2023	01:06	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti7 M23FLU24
17/07/2023	01:11	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti6 M23FLU25
17/07/2023	01:22	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.935	1719	Ti5 M23FLU26
17/07/2023	08:15	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.541	1693	Sampling mussels sulfure PBT2
17/07/2023	08:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Suction sampler 8 SPIDER
17/07/2023	09:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.546	1693	Sampling big mussels in PBT3
17/07/2023	11:12	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	M23-FLU27 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:22	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.670	1728	Sampling M23-FLU28 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:27	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	Sampling M23-FLU29 diffuse
17/07/2023	11:32	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.666	1728	Sampling M23-FLU30 diffuse

7.4.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
16/07/2023	13:27	Nord TE	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.523	1689	Measurement Temperature 4,65°C
16/07/2023	14:42	Montsegur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.537	1699	Measurement T° = 315°C
16/07/2023	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.530	1701	C2a temp: 4.60 - 4.76
16/07/2023	17:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.530	1701	C1b temperature top left 4.85
16/07/2023	20:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Measurement de T°C 5.55°C-5.67
16/07/2023	21:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.539	1700	Probe PEP in place C1a 4.89°C, 4.96°C
16/07/2023	21:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1699	Measurement temperature sur C2b
17/07/2023	24:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.936	1719	Measurement T° = 324°C
17/07/2023	08:03	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.545	1693	Grab temperature probe 4 5.87
17/07/2023	08:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.533	1701	T°C bottom R0a, 11.80°C, 13.76, 15.73
17/07/2023	11:01	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.669	1728	Grab probe temperature ROV

Navigation

7.5. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 843-5

July 19th, Wednesday

Victor launching position Lava lake	37°17,541 N	32°16,796 W	
Launching position NAVIS Y3	37°17,5257 N	32°16,6543 W	
Launching time	01h42	Victor at the bottom	NA
Departure from bottom	02h44	Time Victor on deck	05h11

7.5.1. Objectives

End MERCES experiment Sintra & periph, Mat FeOx lava lake, Sintra, Y3, probes Sintra et Montsegur/Tour Eiffel, Capelinhos

Coordinates :

Sintra		N 37°17.535	W 32°16,499	1614
Lava lake FeOx		N 37°17.541	W32°16.796	1738
Seamon W		N 37°17.47627	W 32°16.78665	1741
Y3-FeOx		N37°17.518	W32°16.663	1727
Sintra inactive quadrats MERCES		N37° 17.47486'	W16.50431'	1644
Coloniser ana sintra inactive		N 37°17.465	W 32°16,792	1739
Quadrats periphery	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.518	1702
Capelinhos FeOx		N37°17.360	W032°15.829	1669

Victor

Descending basket

PBT1(LSLL2)	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	Petit BASKET probe (4 LTgrad)
PBT2 (Céline)		Ibutton chains	3 Probes HTnke + 1LTW

Ascending basket

PBT1, PBT2, PBT3	4 Gaz tights	Probes	small BASKET with probes
			HTnke

NAVIS

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBT3	4 gaz tights + PBT1 (LSLL1), PBT2, PBTI
BASKET 1		TCM3-2 Seamon W + Niskin

Instrumentation

PEP – 6 bags 14 à 19		SUCTION SAMPLER	
----------------------	--	-----------------	--

7.5.2. Operation summary:

Incident ROV at 2h44 – blackout – emergency recovery

7.5.3. Samples

PEP

7.6. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 844-6

2023, July 19th, Wednesday

Victor launching position Lava lake	37°17,541 N	32°16,796 W	
Launching position NAVI5 Y3	37°17,5257 N	32°16,6543 W	
Launching position NAVI6 TE/Montsegur	37°17,3692 N	32°16,4402 W	
Launching position NAVI7 Capelinhos	37°17,4276 N	32°15,7319 W	
Launching time	22h36	Time Victor at the bottom	00h24
Departure from bottom	06h59 July 22nd	Time Victor on deck	08h52

7.6.1. Objectives

End MERCES experiment Sintra & periph, Mat FeOX lava lake, Sintra, Y3, probes Sintra et Montsegur/Tour Eiffel, Capelinhos

Coordinates :

Sintra		N 37°17.535	W 32°16,499	1614
Lava lake FeOx		N 37°17.541	W32°16.796	1738
Seamon W		N 37°17.47627	W 32°16.78665	1741
Y3-FeOx		N37°17.518	W32°16.663	1727
Sintra inactive quadrats MERCES		N37° 17.47486'	W16.50431'	1644
Coloniser ana sintra inactive		N 37°17.465	W 32°16,792	1739
Quadrats périphérie	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.518	1702
Capelinhos FeOx		N37°17.360	W032°15.829	1669

Victor

Descending basket

PBT1(LSLL2)	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	Small BASKET probe (4 LTgrad)
PBT2 (Céline)		Ibutton chains	3 Probes HTnke + 1LTW

Ascending basket

PBT1, PBT2, PBT3	4 Gaz tights	Probes	Small BASKET with probes
			HTnke

NAVI5 (already at the bottom)

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBT3	4 gaz tights + PBT1 (LSLL1), PBT2, PBTI
BASKET 1 (sans fond)		TCM3-2 Seamon W + Niskin

NAVI6

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights bells + PBT4, PBT5 (LSCap6)	4 gaz tights + PBT3
BASKET 1 (sans fond)	TCM3-B & TCM3-C	

NAVI7

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBT1, PBT2, PBT3	4 gaz tights bells + PBT4, PBT5
BASKET 1 (avec fond)	Probes + BASKET probe	BASKET probes avec probes

Instrumentation

PEP – 6 bags 14 à 19		SUCTION SAMPLER	
----------------------	--	-----------------	--

7.6.2. Operations summary:

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep	Comment
20/07/2023	24:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.541	W 032 16.883	1726	At the bottom
20/07/2023	24:26	Lava lake	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.858	1723	Iron mat
20/07/2023	24:31	Lava lake	N 37 17.546	W 032 16.805	1736	Coloniser LSLL1
20/07/2023	24:50	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Deployment Coloniser LSLL2 Fe-Ox
20/07/2023	24:52	Lava lake	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.795	1738	Recovery Coloniser LSLL1
20/07/2023	01:11	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	StartSampling PEP Bag 14 (3min)
20/07/2023	01:15	Lava lake	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.794	1738	Start sampling PEP bag 15

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep	Comment
20/07/2023	01:32	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Sampling iron mat
20/07/2023	01:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.794	1738	Towards Seamon W
20/07/2023	02:05	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.790	1733	Sampling Niskin
20/07/2023	02:08	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.789	1739	Recovery TCM3-2
20/07/2023	02:08	Lucky strike	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.788	1739	Transit towards Y3 with TCM3-2
20/07/2023	02:16	Y3	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.676	1724	Arrival at Y3
20/07/2023	02:27	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1725	Victor wedged at Y3 for black smoker sampling
20/07/2023	02:37	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.671	1725	Measurement temperature T=312°C
20/07/2023	02:38	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1725	T=318°C
20/07/2023	02:38	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1725	T=319.5°C
20/07/2023	02:45	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1725	Sampling Ti1 M23FLU31
20/07/2023	02:52	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.672	1726	Sampling Ti2 M23FLU32
20/07/2023	02:57	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti3 M23FLU33
20/07/2023	03:04	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti4 M23FLU34
20/07/2023	03:22	Y3	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.646	1690	Searching for Elevator NAVI5
20/07/2023	03:41	Elevator	N 37 17.485	W 032 16.637	1688	Navi 5 grabbed in sherpa
20/07/2023	03:48	Elevator	N 37 17.486	W 032 16.635	1688	PBT2
20/07/2023	03:52	Elevator	N 37 17.486	W 032 16.637	1688	PBT1in Navi 5 basket 1
20/07/2023	03:54	Elevator	N 37 17.486	W 032 16.637	1688	Niskin in BASKET
20/07/2023	04:02	Elevator	N 37 17.487	W 032 16.639	1689	TCM3-2 in navi5
20/07/2023	04:09	Elevator	N 37 17.487	W 032 16.640	1689	Exchange gaz tightS BASKET 2
20/07/2023	04:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.485	W 032 16.642	1677	Transit towards Y3-FeOx
20/07/2023	05:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.650	1693	PBTI lost PL5 not found, towards elevator
20/07/2023	05:40	Elevator	N 37 17.480	W 032 16.641	1690	Arrival at NAVI : closing BASKET
20/07/2023	05:54	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.669	1726	Y3
20/07/2023	06:04	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.670	1727	Sampling mussels in PBT3
20/07/2023	06:21	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1727	Suction sampler gastropods SUCTION SAMPLER1
20/07/2023	06:31	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.669	1725	End of suction -broke the device
20/07/2023	06:52	Y3	N 37 17.502	W 032 16.668	1719	Arrival at Y3 : visual structure
20/07/2023	07:00	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.675	1726	Elevator NAVI5 released
20/07/2023	08:14	Y3	N 37 17.484	W 032 16.709	1728	In position to start OTUS
20/07/2023	08:30	Y3	N 37 17.480	W 032 16.697	1729	Bas UBS for the last 15 mn..
20/07/2023	08:55	Y3	N 37 17.491	W 032 16.698	1729	Trying to start OTUS
20/07/2023	10:03	Y3	N 37 17.524	W 032 16.686	1728	UBS good again
20/07/2023	12:05	Y3	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.653	1718	End OTUS Y3, Towards Sintra Inactive
20/07/2023	12:07	Y3	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.655	1719	Start transect video altitude 3m, vélocity 0.2m/s
20/07/2023	12:29	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.507	1616	Arrival Sintra - Fin transect video - fin OTUS - Marqueurs en vue
20/07/2023	12:30	Sintra	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.501	1611	- Fin OTUS
20/07/2023	12:36	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.501	1613	Inspection of smokers for gaz tightS
20/07/2023	12:48	Sintra	N 37 17.529	W 032 16.502	1613	Measurement temperature T° = 219°C
20/07/2023	12:54	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti8 M23FLU35
20/07/2023	13:03	Sintra	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti7 M23FLU36
20/07/2023	13:09	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.501	1613	Ti6 M23FLU37
20/07/2023	13:14	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.502	1613	Ti5 M23FLU38
20/07/2023	13:25	Sintra	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.500	1614	Recovery HTNKE41004
20/07/2023	13:52	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.501	1614	Giving up on installing probe
20/07/2023	13:59	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.503	1614	Start reconstruction of Sintra
20/07/2023	14:50	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.504	1618	End of reconstruction 3D
20/07/2023	14:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.506	1618	Towards Sintra inactive
20/07/2023	14:56	Lucky strike	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.522	1628	En route
20/07/2023	15:01	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.556	1653	Arrival at sintra inactive
20/07/2023	15:06	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.549	1649	Quadrats i1 et i2 + Colonisers Ana
20/07/2023	15:09	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.542	1652	Visualisation Colonisers

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep	Comment
20/07/2023	15:11	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.540	1651	3 Colonisers opened
20/07/2023	15:27	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C left corner quadrat I1, T°C 4.55 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	15:32	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C coin up right corner I2, 4.57
20/07/2023	15:40	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.543	1651	T°C middle on I2 4.57
20/07/2023	15:44	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1651	T°C up right corner, quadrat I2 :4.57°C
20/07/2023	15:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.539	1640	Transit towards tour eiffel
20/07/2023	16:28	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.536	1701	Recovery quadrat SPIDER reference experiment
20/07/2023	16:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.543	1694	Deployment quadrat
20/07/2023	16:51	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1694	Measure T°C bottom left corner quadrat reference SPIDER, 5.62-5.50,5.69 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	16:55	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1694	T°C corner up right reference quadrat SPIDER 5.45°C, 5.42°C
20/07/2023	17:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1694	SPIDER fell
20/07/2023	17:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.542	1694	Quadrat référence SPIDER repositionned
20/07/2023	17:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.542	1694	Tempzrature quadrat reference left corner,6.60°C, 6.81, 7.00, 6.70°C
20/07/2023	17:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.543	1694	T°C up right corner reference quadrat SPIDER, 5.88°C, 6.01, 6.11°C
20/07/2023	18:16	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.540	1693	Recovery SPIDER for deployment
20/07/2023	18:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.541	1694	SPIDER in place on reference quadrat
20/07/2023	18:52	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.516	1691	Arrival Elevator
20/07/2023	18:55	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.514	1691	BASKET blocked when opening : exchange PBTs
20/07/2023	19:07	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.527	1692	Exchanges gaz tightts
20/07/2023	19:29	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.513	1688	Transit tour eiffel
20/07/2023	20:16	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.533	1691	Installing TCM3=C at the North of TEMPO
20/07/2023	20:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.522	1701	Recovery HTnke 29006
20/07/2023	20:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.522	1701	HTnke29009 installed
20/07/2023	20:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.522	1701	LTgrad14 recovered
20/07/2023	20:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.522	1701	LTgrad3 installed
20/07/2023	20:51	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.513	1701	LTmétel 3 recovered
20/07/2023	20:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.514	1701	LTgrad10 installed
20/07/2023	21:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.512	1700	Recovery LTmetal11
20/07/2023	21:11	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.511	1700	LTgrad6 installed
20/07/2023	21:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.527	1691	LTgrad12 recovered
20/07/2023	21:30	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.524	1691	Installing de LTW017
20/07/2023	21:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.515	1691	LTgrad2 installed
20/07/2023	21:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.509	1674	Towards Montségur
20/07/2023	22:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.546	1701	HTNKE29014 installed
20/07/2023	22:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1700	HTnke30012 installed
20/07/2023	22:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.534	1693	Arrival TEMPO area
20/07/2023	22:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.537	1693	Installing BT12
20/07/2023	22:43	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.535	1693	Bt11 installed
20/07/2023	22:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1693	Old chain recovered with one probe
20/07/2023	22:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.530	1693	BT13 installed
20/07/2023	22:53	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.515	1693	Measurement bouton 21 chaîne BT12-4.69°C
20/07/2023	22:54	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.531	1693	Measurement bouton 22 chaîne BT12-4.69°C
20/07/2023	22:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement Bouton 23 chaîne BT12-4.61°C

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep	Comment
20/07/2023	22:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement temperature bouton 24 chaîne BT12 - 4,61°C
20/07/2023	22:59	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature bouton25 chaîne BT12- 4,55°C
20/07/2023	23:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature 1er bouton ? chaîne BT11
20/07/2023	23:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.533	1693	Measurement temperature 2ème bouton BT11
20/07/2023	23:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3ème bouton BT11 - 4.64°C
20/07/2023	23:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement quatrième bouton n°14- 4.68°C
20/07/2023	23:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement bouton 5 n°15 chaîne BT1- 4.66°C
20/07/2023	23:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	1er bouton chaîne BT13 - 5,31°C
20/07/2023	23:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	Measurement temperature 2ème bouton chaîne BT13 - 5,22°C
20/07/2023	23:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3ème bouton chaîne BT13- 6,54°C
20/07/2023	23:25	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature 4ème bouton chaîne BT13 8°C
20/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 5ème bouton BT13 - 7,9°C
20/07/2023	23:32	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.536	1693	6,7°C mineralisation at the top
20/07/2023	23:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature exit of black smoker TEMPO area
20/07/2023	23:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement in focused exit - 42,5
20/07/2023	23:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement in diffusion area - 28°C
20/07/2023	23:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Diffusion flange at 30°C
20/07/2023	23:42	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.537	1693	80°C in focused diffusion
20/07/2023	23:44	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.539	1693	110°C
20/07/2023	23:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.538	1693	125°C
21/07/2023	24:02	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	12°C in shimmering
21/07/2023	24:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.535	1693	51°C smoker
21/07/2023	24:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.542	1695	Towards periphery
21/07/2023	24:31	Périph MS	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.522	1698	POMME P1 in view
21/07/2023	24:56	Périph MS	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.519	1702	T°C 4.46 (probe 4)
21/07/2023	01:00	Périph MS	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.517	1702	T°C 4.45°C (up right corner periphery quadrat)
21/07/2023	01:21	Lucky strike	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.553	1696	Diffusion area mussels flat POI
21/07/2023	01:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.553	1695	T°C 4.46 (probe 4)
21/07/2023	01:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.553	1695	T°C in sediments 4.47°C
21/07/2023	01:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.557	1696	Super patch de mussels/white mat
21/07/2023	01:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.557	1696	T°C 15.-16.17-23...
21/07/2023	01:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.560	1696	Ideal area for experimentation
21/07/2023	01:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.557	1696	T°C 5.22
21/07/2023	01:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.558	1696	T°C 25°C-22°C
21/07/2023	01:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.560	1696	T°C white mat 9.52-9.21°C
21/07/2023	01:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.563	1696	Panorama of the area
21/07/2023	01:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.556	1695	Reconstruction 3D new area, OTUS
21/07/2023	07:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.520	1688	End of OTUS
21/07/2023	07:22	Lucky strike	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.524	1683	Release elevator
21/07/2023	08:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.218	W 032 15.690	1696	Start OTUS towards CAPELINHOS. Victor at Southeast 37°17'12.3N & 32°15'40.6 W.
21/07/2023	10:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.356	W 032 15.828	1672	Arrival at CAPELINHOS.
21/07/2023	10:16	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.835	1661	Start reconstruction 3D cap 180
21/07/2023	11:55	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.836	1667	End of 3D Reconstruction Capelinhos.
21/07/2023	11:59	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.831	1668	Arrival at iron mats Cap-FeOx
21/07/2023	12:08	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.831	1669	temperature on the left 21°C
21/07/2023	12:12	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.832	1669	Temperature grey zone 38°- 45°C

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep	Comment
21/07/2023	12:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1669	Sampling M23-FLU39
21/07/2023	12:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU40
21/07/2023	13:00	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.832	1669	Sampling M23-FLU41
21/07/2023	13:15	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU42
21/07/2023	13:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	1669	Sampling M23-Cap-FeOx dans PBT4
21/07/2023	14:00	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.834	1668	Recovery LS-Cap5
21/07/2023	14:06	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	1668	Deployment LS-Cap6
21/07/2023	15:25	Capelinhos	N 37 17.348	W 032 15.785	1675	Manips elevator : PBT, gaz tight & probes
21/07/2023	16:22	Capelinhos	N 37 17.352	W 032 15.781	1675	The bottom of BASKET 1 of the elevator flew out with a probe on it
21/07/2023	16:48	Capelinhos	N 37 17.341	W 032 15.822	1567	Elevator blocked at 1400 m depth
21/07/2023	18:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1668	Start sampling mussels PBT2
21/07/2023	19:19	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1659	Sampling chimney in PBT1
21/07/2023	19:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1659	temperature 307°C
21/07/2023	19:48	Capelinhos	N 37 17.365	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti8 M23FLU43
21/07/2023	19:53	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1658	Ti5 M23FLU44
21/07/2023	20:01	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti7 M23FLU45
21/07/2023	20:06	Capelinhos	N 37 17.356	W 032 15.828	1658	Ti6 M23FLU46
21/07/2023	20:22	Capelinhos	N 37 17.344	W 032 15.856	1675	Arrival at the start of OTUS Capelinhos. 37°17'20.3"N 32°15'51.6"W
21/07/2023	20:30	Capelinhos	N 37 17.339	W 032 15.860	1676	Start OTUS LABEL 200.
22/07/2023	01:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17.370	W 032 15.852	1672	Start transect Tour Eiffel - Altitude 3m, 0.25 knots - start transect
22/07/2023	03:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.528	1682	Arrival at Tour Eiffel
22/07/2023	03:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.543	1693	Bell SPIDER deployed since 36h
22/07/2023	04:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1693	T°C 5.18°C, 5.14°C, 5.26°C, 5.45 °C reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	04:03	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1693	5.68°C, 5.73, 5.77°C on reference quadrat area of SPIDER, patch of mussels with microbial mats
22/07/2023	04:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.541	1693	5.73°C, on reference quadrat area SPIDER, patch of mussels with microbial mats
22/07/2023	04:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.540	1693	6.16°C sur small mussels reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	04:18	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1693	106°C max measured at the top of reference quadrat
22/07/2023	04:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.540	1693	Sampling reference quadrat in PBT3
22/07/2023	04:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.545	1694	Arrival at Soleil
22/07/2023	05:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T1 4.71
22/07/2023	05:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T2 pushed in ~20°C
22/07/2023	05:19	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T3 at the surface of dark grey orange area 4.62
22/07/2023	05:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T3 inside ~ 43°C
22/07/2023	05:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T5 on grey
22/07/2023	05:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.541	1697	Measurement T4 on light grey surface 6.44
22/07/2023	05:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T6 inside 44°C
22/07/2023	05:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T7 on orange mat 5.05
22/07/2023	05:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T8 probe inside orange mats ~ 41°C
22/07/2023	05:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.541	1697	Installing LTgrad 20
22/07/2023	05:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	HTNKE 41003 installed
22/07/2023	06:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.539	1696	LTgrad8 installed
22/07/2023	06:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.260	W 032 16.522	1691	Leaving bottom

7.6.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
20/07/2023	24:50	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Deployment Coloniser LSL2 Fe-Ox
20/07/2023	24:52	Lava lake	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.795	1738	Recovery Coloniser LSL1
20/07/2023	02:08	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.789	1739	Recovery TCM3-2
20/07/2023	20:16	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.533	1691	Installing TCM3-C au nord de TEMPO
20/07/2023	20:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.522	1701	Recovery HTnke 29006
20/07/2023	20:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.522	1701	HTnke29009 installed
20/07/2023	20:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.522	1701	LTgrad14 recovered
20/07/2023	20:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.522	1701	LTgrad3 installed
20/07/2023	20:51	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.513	1701	LTmtal 3 recovered
20/07/2023	20:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.514	1701	LTgrad10 installed
20/07/2023	21:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.512	1700	Recovery LTmetal11
20/07/2023	21:11	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.511	1700	LTgrad6 installed
20/07/2023	21:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.527	1691	LTgrad12 recovered
20/07/2023	21:30	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.524	1691	Installing de LTW017
20/07/2023	21:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.515	1691	LTgrad2 installed
20/07/2023	22:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.546	1701	HTNKE29014 installed
20/07/2023	22:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1700	HTnke30012 installed
20/07/2023	22:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.537	1693	Installing BT12
20/07/2023	22:43	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.535	1693	Bt11 installed
20/07/2023	22:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.530	1693	BT13 installed
21/07/2023	14:00	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.834	1668	Recovery LS-Cap5
21/07/2023	14:06	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	1668	Deployment LS-Cap6
22/07/2023	05:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.541	1697	Installing de LTgrad 20
22/07/2023	06:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.539	1696	LTgrad8 installed

7.6.4 Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
20/07/2023	01:11	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	StartSampling PEP Bag 14 M23-LL-PEP
20/07/2023	01:15	Lava lake	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.794	1738	Start de sampling PEP bag 15 M23-LL-PEP
20/07/2023	01:32	Lava lake	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Sampling iron mat M23-LLFeOx
20/07/2023	02:05	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.790	1733	Sampling Niskin
20/07/2023	02:45	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1725	Sampling Ti1 M23FLU31
20/07/2023	02:52	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.672	1726	Sampling Ti2 M23FLU32
20/07/2023	02:57	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti3 M23FLU33
20/07/2023	03:04	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti4 M23FLU34
20/07/2023	06:04	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.670	1727	Sampling mussels dans PBT3
20/07/2023	06:21	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1727	Suction samplerration gastropods SUCTION SAMPLER1
20/07/2023	12:54	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti8 M23FLU35
20/07/2023	13:03	Sintra	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti7 M23FLU36
20/07/2023	13:09	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.501	1613	Ti6 M23FLU37
20/07/2023	13:14	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.502	1613	Ti5 M23FLU38
21/07/2023	12:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1669	Sampling M23-FLU39
21/07/2023	12:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU40
21/07/2023	13:00	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.832	1669	Sampling M23-FLU41
21/07/2023	13:15	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU42
21/07/2023	13:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	1669	Sampling M23-Cap-FeOx PBT4
21/07/2023	18:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1668	Start sampling mussels PBT2
21/07/2023	19:19	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1659	Sampling chminey in PBT1 M23- CapChem
21/07/2023	19:48	Capelinhos	N 37 17.365	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti8 M23FLU43
21/07/2023	19:53	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1658	Ti5 M23FLU44
21/07/2023	20:01	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti7 M23FLU45
21/07/2023	20:06	Capelinhos	N 37 17.356	W 032 15.828	1658	Ti6 M23FLU46
22/07/2023	04:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.540	1693	Sampling reference quadrat PBT3

7.6.5 Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
20/07/2023	02:37	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.671	1725	Measurement temperature T=312°C
20/07/2023	12:48	Sintra	N 37 17.529	W 032 16.502	1613	Measurement temperature T° = 219°C
20/07/2023	15:27	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C left corner quadrat I1,T°C 4.55 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	15:32	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C coin up right corner I2, 4.57
20/07/2023	15:40	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.543	1651	T°C middle on I2 4.57
20/07/2023	15:44	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1651	T°C up right corner, quadrat I2: 4.57°C
20/07/2023	16:51	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1694	Measure T°C bottom left corner quadrat reference SPIDER, 5.62-5.50,5.69 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	16:55	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1694	T°C corner up right reference quadrat SPIDER 5.45°C, 5.42°C
20/07/2023	17:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.542	1694	Temperature quadrat reference left corner,6.60°C, 6.81, 7.00, 6.70°C
20/07/2023	17:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.543	1694	T°C up right corner reference quadrat SPIDER, 5.88°C, 6.01, 6.11°C
20/07/2023	22:53	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.515	1693	Measurement bouton 21 chaîne BT12- 4.69°C
20/07/2023	22:54	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.531	1693	Measurement bouton 22 chaîne BT12- 4.69°C
20/07/2023	22:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement Bouton 23 chaîne BT12- 4.61°C
20/07/2023	22:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement temperature bouton 24 chaîne BT12 - 4,61°C
20/07/2023	22:59	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature bouton25 chaîne BT12- 4,55°C
20/07/2023	23:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature 1er bouton ? chaîne BT11
20/07/2023	23:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.533	1693	Measurement temperature 2ème bouton BT11
20/07/2023	23:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3ème bouton BT11 - 4.64°C
20/07/2023	23:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement quatrième bouton n°14- 4.68°C
20/07/2023	23:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement bouton 5 n°15 chaîne BT1- 4.66°C
20/07/2023	23:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	1er bouton chaîne BT13 - 5,31°C
20/07/2023	23:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	Measurement temperature 2ème bouton chaîne BT13 - 5,22°C
20/07/2023	23:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3ème bouton chaîne BT13- 6,54°C
20/07/2023	23:25	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature 4ème bouton chaîne BT13 8°C
20/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 5ème bouton BT13 - 7,9°C
20/07/2023	23:32	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.536	1693	6,7°C mineralisation at the top
20/07/2023	23:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature exit of black smoker TEMPO area
20/07/2023	23:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement in focused exit - 42,5
20/07/2023	23:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement in diffusion area - 28°C
20/07/2023	23:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Diffusion flange at 30°C
20/07/2023	23:42	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.537	1693	80°C in focused diffusion
20/07/2023	23:44	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.539	1693	110°C
20/07/2023	23:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.538	1693	125°C
21/07/2023	24:02	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	12°C in shimmering
21/07/2023	24:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.535	1693	51°C smoker
21/07/2023	24:56	Périph MS	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.519	1702	T°C 4.46 (probe 4)
21/07/2023	01:00	Périph MS	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.517	1702	T°C 4.45°C (up right corner periphery quadrat)
21/07/2023	01:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.553	1695	T°C 4.46 (probe 4)

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
21/07/2023	01:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.553	1695	T°C in sediments 4.47°C
21/07/2023	01:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.557	1696	T°C 15.-16.17-23...
21/07/2023	01:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.557	1696	T°C 5.22
21/07/2023	01:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.558	1696	T°C 25°C-22°C
21/07/2023	01:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.560	1696	T°C white mat 9.52-9.21°C
21/07/2023	12:08	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.831	1669	temperature on the left 21°C
21/07/2023	12:12	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.832	1669	Temperature grey zone 38°- 45°C
21/07/2023	12:08	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.831	1669	Grab temperature mat fer
21/07/2023	19:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1659	Grab de temperature 307°C
22/07/2023	04:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1693	T°C 5.18°C, 5.14°C, 5.26°C, 5.45 °C reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	04:03	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1693	5.68°C, 5.73, 5.77°C on reference quadrat area of SPIDER, patch of mussels with microbial mats
22/07/2023	04:04	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.541	1693	5.73°C, on reference quadrat area SPIDER, patch of mussels with microbial mats
22/07/2023	04:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.540	1693	6.16°C sur small mussels reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	04:18	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1693	106°C max measured at the top of reference quadrat
22/07/2023	05:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T1 4.71
22/07/2023	05:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T2 pushed in ~20°C
22/07/2023	05:19	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T3 at the surface of dark grey orange area 4.62
22/07/2023	05:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T3 inside ~ 43°C
22/07/2023	05:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T5 on grey
22/07/2023	05:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.541	1697	Measurement T4 on light grey surface 6.44
22/07/2023	05:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T6 inside 44°C
22/07/2023	05:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T7 on orange mat 5.05
22/07/2023	05:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T8 probe inside orange mats ~ 41°C

7.6.6 Reconstruction 3

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
20/07/2023	13:59	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.503	1614	Startreconstruction de Sintra
20/07/2023	14:50	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.504	1618	Fin manip reconstruction 3D
21/07/2023	10:16	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.835	1661	Démarrage reconstruction 3D cap 180
21/07/2023	11:55	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.836	1667	Fin de Reconstruction 3D de Capelinhos.

7.6.7 OTUS

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
20/07/2023	08:14	Y3	N 37 17.484	W 032 16.709	1728	En position pour startOTUS
20/07/2023	08:30	Y3	N 37 17.480	W 032 16.697	1729	La BUC est mauvaise depuis plus de 15 mn..on ne peut pas commencer OTUS...
20/07/2023	08:55	Y3	N 37 17.491	W 032 16.698	1729	Tentative en automatique OTUS startde Depil sud=nord1
20/07/2023	10:03	Y3	N 37 17.524	W 032 16.686	1728	on a retrouvé une bonne BUC...
20/07/2023	12:05	Y3	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.653	1718	Fin OTUS Y3
20/07/2023	12:07	Y3 - Sintra	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.655	1719	Starttransect video Y3 – Sintra altitude 3m, vélocité 0.2m/s
20/07/2023	12:30	Sintra	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.501	1611	- Fin OTUS
21/07/2023	01:59	Cimendef	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.556	1695	OTUS nouvelle zone Montsegur
21/07/2023	08:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.218	W 032 15.690	1696	StartOTUS towards CAPELINHOS. 37°17'12.3N et 32°15'40.6 W.
21/07/2023	20:30	Capelinhos	N 37 17.339	W 032 15.860	1676	Départ OTUS LABEL 200.
22/07/2023	01:15	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.370	W 032 15.852	1672	transect Capelinhos Tour Eiffel - Altitude 3m, 0.25 nœuds - starttransect

7.6.8 Navigation

7.7 MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 845-7

July 22, Saturday, 2023

Victor launching position	N 37 17.3181	W 032 16.5016	
Mouillage Seamon Est	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.556	target
Launching time	17h57	VICTOR At the bottom	19h41
Departure from bottom	08h30 July 23	Time Victor on board	10h12

7.7.1. Objectives

Seamon E, MERCES, Y3, Sintra sampling

Coordinates:

Sintra-FeOx		N 37°17.533	W 32°16,507	
Sintra inactive		See POI quadrat & pyramides Dive 844-6		
Periphery	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.518	1702

Victor

Descending basket

WIFI	4 Gaz tights		
PBT2	PBT3	croc	

Ascending basket

WIFI	4 Gaz tights bells	LTW	
PBT1	PBT3		

NAVI8

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights-bells + PBT1 (LSWS1)	4 gaz tights + SPIDER + PBT
BASKET 1 (sans fond)		2 POMMEs + TCM3-A + hook

Instrumentation

PEP – 2 bags 18 & 19		SUCTION SAMPLER	
----------------------	--	-----------------	--

7.7.2. Operations summary:

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
22/07/2023	19:41	Lucky strike	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.494	1693	Arrival At the bottom
22/07/2023	19:52	Lucky strike	N 37 17.311	W 032 16.522	1691	Transit Seamon E
22/07/2023	19:54	Lucky strike	N 37 17.314	W 032 16.548	1695	Seamon E
22/07/2023	19:56	Seamon E	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.546	1694	Start installing Seamon E
22/07/2023	20:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.317	W 032 16.558	1700	grit bag removed
22/07/2023	20:06	Seamon E	N 37 17.317	W 032 16.554	1700	Second bag removed
22/07/2023	20:35	Seamon E	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.535	1693	Station in place
22/07/2023	20:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.533	1693	Installing 4 grit bags on the station
22/07/2023	21:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.535	1694	wifi in place : TEMPO don't communicate
22/07/2023	21:32	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1694	wifi removed
22/07/2023	21:34	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.534	1694	wifi in place : no more connection
22/07/2023	22:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.535	1689	TCM3-A hooked
22/07/2023	22:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.547	1692	PEP1 on quadrat SPIDER reference, 6.12°C, 6.29, 6.50, ça , max 6.82. PEP is working. 43 secondes
22/07/2023	22:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.545	1692	Suction sampler 1 on reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	22:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.553	1695	LTW020 recovered
22/07/2023	23:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.541	1697	View C1a
22/07/2023	23:25	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.540	1699	Start PEP 2 C1a - 4.68°C
22/07/2023	23:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.536	1700	PEP 3 C1a-cg, 4.5°C
22/07/2023	23:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1700	Suction sampler 2 C1a-cg
23/07/2023	24:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.539	1695	TEMPO did not turn on

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	24:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.529	1699	Arrival at Montségur - DEAFs
23/07/2023	24:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.538	1698	Measurement de T°: 312.8°C - 313°C
23/07/2023	24:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.540	1698	M23 FLU 47
23/07/2023	01:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23 Flu48
23/07/2023	01:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU49
23/07/2023	01:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU50
23/07/2023	01:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 4 C1 bcg Temperature T= 7.60 - 6.87
23/07/2023	01:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.535	1700	C1 Bcg SUCTION SAMPLER3
23/07/2023	02:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.531	1700	PEP 5 in c2a T=4.76 -4.75
23/07/2023	02:16	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 6 in RO -CENTER T= 6.68 - 4.80
23/07/2023	02:22	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1700	PEP 7 C2bcg T= 4.78 - 4.80
23/07/2023	02:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.533	1700	Suction sampler4 in C2bcg
23/07/2023	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1699	Star PEP 8 in C1b
23/07/2023	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1698	Start PEP 9 in C2b
23/07/2023	03:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.532	1698	SUCTION SAMPLER 4 in center C2acg
23/07/2023	03:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.533	1698	Start sampling C2a-ag PBT2
23/07/2023	03:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.519	1701	PEP 11 périphérie P1 T= 4.50
23/07/2023	03:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.520	1701	Suction sampler 6 in center P1
23/07/2023	04:16	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.531	1698	Arrival montsegur
23/07/2023	04:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.535	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
23/07/2023	04:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.307	W 032 16.513	1688	Elevator : exchanges PBT et gaz tight
23/07/2023	05:08	Lucky strike	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.563	1675	Transit towards sintra inactive
23/07/2023	05:28	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.553	1647	Arrival at quadra I1 et I2
23/07/2023	05:33	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Start sampling PEP 13 T= 4.60°C
23/07/2023	05:35	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Sampling SUCTION SAMPLER Jar 7 au centre I1
23/07/2023	05:43	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling PEP 13 T=4.55°C I2
23/07/2023	05:46	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling SUCTION SAMPLER 8 I2
23/07/2023	05:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.545	1647	Direction towards West Sintra FeOX
23/07/2023	05:55	Lucky strike	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.538	1639	Shimmering area to sample Ti bell
23/07/2023	05:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.538	1640	probe temperature ROV
23/07/2023	06:00	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.538	1640	Measurement temperature 77°C
23/07/2023	06:02	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.539	1640	Measurement Temperature other area 99°C
23/07/2023	06:16	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.540	1640	Sampling M23-FLU51 TiBell 8
23/07/2023	06:21	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU52 Ti Bell 7
23/07/2023	06:26	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.537	1640	Sampling M23-FLU53 Ti Bell 5
23/07/2023	06:31	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU54 Ti Bell 6
23/07/2023	06:54	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.491	1619	Deployment LSSW1
23/07/2023	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.486	1619	T=4.60°C – LSSW1
23/07/2023	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.541	W 032 16.487	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-WSF Bag 18 non filtered
23/07/2023	07:02	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.539	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-SWF Bag 19 filtered
23/07/2023	07:15	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.540	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-WS-FeOx
23/07/2023	07:18	Lucky strike	N 37 17.537	W 032 16.493	1603	Transit towards Seamon Est
23/07/2023	07:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1692	Ready to cut buoyancy device
23/07/2023	07:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.523	1698	TCM3 at the bottom - site hydroctopus – departure from bottom after releasing the elevator NAVI 8

7.7.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
22/07/2023	22:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.535	1689	TCM3-A hooked & recovered
22/07/2023	22:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.553	1695	LTW020 recovered
23/07/2023	06:54	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.491	1619	Deployment LSSW1

7.7.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
22/07/2023	22:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.547	1692	PEP1 on reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	22:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.545	1692	Suction sampler 1 on reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	23:25	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.540	1699	Start PEP 2 C1a – 4.68°C
22/07/2023	23:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.536	1700	PEP 3 C1a-cg, 4.5°C
22/07/2023	23:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1700	Suction sampler 2 C1a-cg
23/07/2023	24:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.540	1698	M23FLU47
23/07/2023	01:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU48
23/07/2023	01:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU49
23/07/2023	01:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU50
23/07/2023	01:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 4 C1 bcg T= 7.60 - 6.87
23/07/2023	01:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.535	1700	C1 Bcg SUCTION SAMPLER3
23/07/2023	02:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.531	1700	PEP 5 in c2a T=4.76 -4.75
23/07/2023	02:16	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 6 in R0 -CENTER T= 6.68 - 4.80
23/07/2023	02:22	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1700	PEP 7 C2bcg T= 4.78 - 4.80
23/07/2023	02:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.533	1700	Suction sampler 4 in C2bcg
23/07/2023	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1699	Star PEP 8 in C1b
23/07/2023	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1698	Start PEP 9 in C2b
23/07/2023	03:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.532	1698	SUCTION SAMPLER 5 in center C2acg
						PEP10
23/07/2023	03:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.533	1698	C2a-ag dans PBT2
23/07/2023	03:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.519	1701	PEP 11 periphery P1 T= 4.50
23/07/2023	03:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.520	1701	Suction sampler 6 in center P1
23/07/2023	04:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.535	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
23/07/2023	05:33	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Start sampling PEP 12 T= 4.60°C
23/07/2023	05:35	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Sampling SUCTION SAMPLER Jar 7 au centre I1
23/07/2023	05:43	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling PEP 13 T=4.55°C I2
23/07/2023	05:46	Sintra inactive	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling SUCTION SAMPLER 8 I2
23/07/2023	06:16	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.540	1640	Sampling M23-FLU51 TiBell 8
23/07/2023	06:21	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU52 Ti Bell 7
23/07/2023	06:26	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.537	1640	Sampling M23-FLU53 Ti Bell 5
23/07/2023	06:31	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU54 Ti Bell 6
23/07/2023	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.541	W 032 16.487	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-WSF Bag 18 non filtered
23/07/2023	07:02	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.539	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-SWF Bag 19 filtered
23/07/2023	07:15	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.540	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-WS-FeOx

7.7.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
22/07/2023	22:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.547	1692	Measurement T°C on reference quadrat SPIDER – max 6,82°C
23/07/2023	24:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.538	1698	Measurement de T°: 312.8°C DEAFS
23/07/2023	06:00	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.538	1640	Measurement temperature 77°C
23/07/2023	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.486	1619	T=4.60°C – LSSW1

7.7.6. Navigation

7.8. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 846-8

July 23 2023, Sunday

Victor launching position	37°17.3181 N	32°16.5016 W	
Mouillage Flotta recovery Seamon E	37°17.319 N	32°16.556 W	1704
Mouillage NAVI9	37°17,3662 N	32°16,4729 W	
Launching time	18h39	Arrival At the bottom	20h04
Departure from bottom	lundi 24 juillet 07h06	Time Victor on board	08h52

7.8.1. Objectives

Verification Seamon E, Hooking Seamon E, COMBO, bells soleil, Y3-FeOx, White Castle, Montsegur

Coordinates:

Seamon West		37N 17.4783	32W 16.8099	target
Y3-FeOx	Cap 315	N37 17.518	W32 16.663	1727
MERCES P1	Montsegur periphery	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.518	1702
Site Jozée	Sud Montsegur, POI in MIMOSA			

Victor

Descending basket

PBT1	4 Gaz tights	HTW	HTnke
PBT2	WIFI		

Ascending basket

	4 Gaz tights		

NAVI9

	descending	Ascending
BASKET 2	4 gaz tights + PBT3	4 gaz tights bells + PBT1 + PBT2
BASKET 1 (sans fond)	1 quadrat	1 POMME

Instrumentation

PEP – 2 bags 18 & 19		SUCTION SAMPLER	
----------------------	--	-----------------	--

7.8.2. Operations summary

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	20:17	Lucky strike	N 37 17.315	W 032 16.549	1692	Inspection buoyancy device
23/07/2023	20:19	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.538	1693	Arrival at seamon Est
23/07/2023	20:23	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.534	1695	test wifi
23/07/2023	20:33	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.537	1695	Putting away wifi
23/07/2023	20:35	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.534	1694	Adjusting weight with grit bag
23/07/2023	20:59	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.536	1693	Buoyancy device hooked
23/07/2023	21:03	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.537	1695	End Seamon Est
23/07/2023	21:28	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.852	1708	Arrival at White Castle
23/07/2023	21:41	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Measurement of temperature = 320°C
23/07/2023	21:49	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.869	1708	Ti5 M23FLU55
23/07/2023	21:54	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti6 M23FLU56
23/07/2023	22:01	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti7 M23FLU57
23/07/2023	22:07	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti8 M23FLU58
23/07/2023	22:17	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.867	1708	HTW005 installed
23/07/2023	22:33	White Castle	N 37 17.390	W 032 16.863	1721	HTWN021 recovered for displacement towards Montségur
23/07/2023	22:43	White Castle	N 37 17.389	W 032 16.861	1721	HTnke41001 installed

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	22:45	White Castle	N 37 17.391	W 032 16.863	1722	Start survey WC
23/07/2023	23:10	White Castle	N 37 17.459	W 032 16.722	1708	End survey WC
23/07/2023	23:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.459	W 032 16.722	1707	Transit towards Y3
23/07/2023	23:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.676	1723	Arrival at Y3-FeOx
23/07/2023	23:35	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1727	Sampling M23-PEP-Y3 FeOx Bag 19 4.56°C
23/07/2023	23:45	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.673	1727	Sampling M23-PEP-Y3 FeOx Bag 18 NF 3 min
23/07/2023	23:57	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.670	1727	Sampling M23-Y3-FeOx 1 godet PBT1
24/07/2023	24:10	Lucky strike	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.670	1727	Transit towards Tour Eiffel
24/07/2023	24:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.536	1685	Arrival at COMBO area
24/07/2023	24:46	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.538	1687	Remove bell
24/07/2023	24:49	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.538	1687	Sampling mussels in PBT2
24/07/2023	24:57	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.538	1687	Picking up old casimir
24/07/2023	01:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.538	1687	Start Measurement temperature 1 probe 6 on the COMBO area - 6°C-6,4°C
24/07/2023	01:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.537	1687	Start Measurement temperature 2 - 28°
24/07/2023	01:50	Elevator	N 37 17.271	W 032 16.476	1688	Elevator
24/07/2023	01:55	Elevator	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.483	1691	recovery quadrat P1
24/07/2023	01:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.482	1685	transit towards Soleil, South tour eiffel
24/07/2023	02:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.315	W 032 16.534	1693	hydroctopus
24/07/2023	02:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.547	1692	Arrival at soleil
24/07/2023	02:20	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.545	1697	grab temperature probe ROV
24/07/2023	02:27	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.545	1697	Measurement temperature = 72°C
24/07/2023	02:35	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti1 M23FLU59
24/07/2023	02:43	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti2 M23FLU60
24/07/2023	02:48	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.545	1697	Ti3 M23FLU61
24/07/2023	02:56	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti4 M23FLU62
24/07/2023	03:29	Montsegur	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.539	1699	HTW021 installed
24/07/2023	03:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.533	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
24/07/2023	04:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1701	SUCTION SAMPLER – small shrimp
24/07/2023	04:18	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.541	1700	Looking for Pomme 1
24/07/2023	04:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.525	1699	Close to POMME 1 to uninstall quadrat P1
24/07/2023	04:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.520	1702	Drop quadrat P1
24/07/2023	04:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.509	1701	transit towards NAVI9
24/07/2023	04:41	Elevator	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.496	1695	Arrival elevator
24/07/2023	04:43	Elevator	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.486	1692	Dropping POMME1 in elevator NAVI9
24/07/2023	04:55	Lucky strike	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.530	1700	Departure for south site montsegur
24/07/2023	04:57	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.260	W 032 16.551	1698	futur zone mat celine
24/07/2023	05:04	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.565	1697	1.08 m de hauteur
24/07/2023	05:12	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.270	W 032 16.567	1697	Shrimp at the top
24/07/2023	05:16	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.270	W 032 16.566	1697	small mussels area and gastropods
24/07/2023	05:21	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.269	W 032 16.569	1697	Shimmering, white mats, small mussels
24/07/2023	05:24	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.568	1696	Patch of small mussels
24/07/2023	05:25	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.265	W 032 16.565	1695	Active small chimneys
24/07/2023	05:27	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.266	W 032 16.565	1696	Orange mat
24/07/2023	05:28	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.265	W 032 16.565	1696	Smoking chimney, grey
24/07/2023	05:42	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.565	1697	Measurement T°C max 108°C
24/07/2023	05:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.565	1697	Temperature close to big mussels 8.10°C
24/07/2023	05:45	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.64°C on average mussels
24/07/2023	05:46	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.61 in mat/mussels
24/07/2023	05:48	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.269	W 032 16.566	1697	4.75 on very small mussels/gastropods transparent
24/07/2023	05:55	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.566	1696	Small gastropod area
24/07/2023	05:56	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	5.04 on gastropods
24/07/2023	06:02	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.271	W 032 16.563	1696	Orange mats at the periphery
24/07/2023	06:10	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C 5.45 on small/average mussels
24/07/2023	06:12	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C average mussels 5.63
24/07/2023	06:13	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C on gastropods 7.52
24/07/2023	06:14	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C white area 9.69°C
24/07/2023	06:15	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 7.15 on small mussels
24/07/2023	06:16	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 6.26°C

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C average mussels 6.40°C
24/07/2023	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C orange mats 10.53 °C
24/07/2023	06:19	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.567	1697	T°C small crack 24°C
24/07/2023	06:22	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	Small fluid exit
24/07/2023	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 26.5°C
24/07/2023	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	Probe deeper T°C 61°C (2 cm)
24/07/2023	06:25	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.566	1697	T°C probe deepen at 80.6°C
24/07/2023	06:27	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	Big mussels 6.21°C
24/07/2023	06:28	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C bigger mussels 5.0°C
24/07/2023	06:30	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	Black gastropods
24/07/2023	06:32	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Video sequence : several gastropods, pycno, polynoids, amphipods
24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction sampler on gastropods, Suction sampler 3
24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction sampler jar 4, mussel area
24/07/2023	06:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.272	W 032 16.569	1697	Suction sampler jar 5
24/07/2023	07:10	Cimendef	N 37 17.227	W 032 16.587	1585	Departure from bottom at 07h06

7.8.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	22:17	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.867	1708	HTW005 installed
23/07/2023	22:33	White Castle	N 37 17.390	W 032 16.863	1721	HTWN021 recovered towards Montségur
23/07/2023	22:43	White Castle	N 37 17.389	W 032 16.861	1721	HTnke41001 installed
24/07/2023	03:29	Montsegur	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.539	1699	HTWN021 installed

7.8.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	21:49	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.869	1708	Ti5 M23FLU55
23/07/2023	21:54	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti6 M23FLU56
23/07/2023	22:01	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti7 M23FLU57
23/07/2023	22:07	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti8 M23FLU58
23/07/2023	23:35	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1727	M23-PEP-Y3 Bag 19 4.56°C
23/07/2023	23:45	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.673	1727	M23-PEP-Y3 FeOx Bag 18 NF 3 min
23/07/2023	23:57	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.670	1727	M23-Y3-FeOx PBT1
24/07/2023	24:49	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.538	1687	Sampling mussels in PBT2
24/07/2023	02:35	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti1 M23FLU59
24/07/2023	02:43	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti2 M23FLU60
24/07/2023	02:48	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.545	1697	Ti3 M23FLU61
24/07/2023	02:56	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti4 M23FLU62
24/07/2023	03:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.533	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
24/07/2023	04:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1701	shrimp SUCTION SAMPLER 1 & 2
24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction sampler in gastropods area, Suction sampler 3
24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction sampler jar 4, mussels area
24/07/2023	06:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.272	W 032 16.569	1697	Suction sampler jar 5

7.8.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	21:41	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Measurement temperature = 320°C
24/07/2023	01:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.538	1687	Start Measurement temperature 1 probe 6 on the COMBO area - 6°C-6,4°C
24/07/2023	01:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.537	1687	Start Measurement temperature 2 - 28°
24/07/2023	02:27	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.545	1697	Measurement temperature = 72°C
24/07/2023	05:42	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.565	1697	Measurement T°C max 108°C
24/07/2023	05:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.565	1697	Temperature close to big mussels 8.10°C
24/07/2023	05:45	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.64°C on average mussels
24/07/2023	05:46	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.61 in mat/mussels

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
23/07/2023	21:41	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Measurement temperature = 320°C
24/07/2023	05:48	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.269	W 032 16.566	1697	4.75 on very small mussels/gastropods transparent
24/07/2023	05:56	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	5.04 on gastropods
24/07/2023	06:10	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C 5.45 on small/average mussels
24/07/2023	06:12	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C average mussels 5.63
24/07/2023	06:13	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C on gastropods 7.52
24/07/2023	06:14	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C white area 9.69°C
24/07/2023	06:15	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 7.15 on small mussels
24/07/2023	06:16	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 6.26°C
24/07/2023	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C average mussels 6.40°C
24/07/2023	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C orange mats 10.53 °C
24/07/2023	06:19	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.567	1697	T°C small crack 24°C
24/07/2023	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 26.5°C
24/07/2023	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	Probe deeper T°C 61°C (2 cm)
24/07/2023	06:25	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.566	1697	T°C probe deepen at 80.6°C
24/07/2023	06:27	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	Big mussels 6.21°C
24/07/2023	06:28	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C bigger mussels 5.0°C

7.8.6. Navigation

7.9. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 847-9

July 24th, Monday

Victor launching position Seamon W	37°17.3181 N	32°16.5016 W	
Mouillage Flotta déplacement Seamon W	37°17.4783 N	32°16.8099 W	target
Launching time	19h11	Arrival At the bottom	20h35
Departure from bottom	07h27 July 15th	Time Victor on board	09h12

7.9.1. Objectives

Verification Seamon W, gaz tights West, current meter, mussels & gastropods south crystal

Coordinates:

Seamon West		37°17.4783 N	32°16.8099 W	target
-------------	--	--------------	--------------	--------

Victor

Descending basket

PBT2	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	
Cylindre SMASH	WIFI		

Ascending basket

PBT2	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	
	WIFI		

Instrumentation

		SUCTION SAMPLER	
--	--	-----------------	--

7.9.2. Operations summary:

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	20:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.399	W 032 16.901	1693	Arrival At the bottom
24/07/2023	20:42	Seamon W	N 37 17.467	W 032 16.814	1737	Arrival at Seamon W
24/07/2023	20:49	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.813	1738	Removing grit bags
24/07/2023	20:59	Seamon W	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.813	1737	Displacement device released
24/07/2023	21:11	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.784	1737	Station Seamon W in place
24/07/2023	21:22	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.786	1736	Triggering Niskin
24/07/2023	21:27	Seamon W	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.785	1739	1 grit bag put on the station
24/07/2023	21:32	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.784	1739	WIFI connected
24/07/2023	22:03	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.786	1739	Test WIFI check!! Seamon W is working!
24/07/2023	22:08	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.789	1739	TCM3-2
24/07/2023	22:11	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.788	1738	Installing cylindre SMASH
24/07/2023	22:16	South Crystal	N 37 17.476	W 032 16.784	1738	Start transit towards South Crystal
24/07/2023	22:29	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.930	1717	Arrival at South Crystal
24/07/2023	22:40	South Crystal	N 37 17.430	W 032 16.939	1718	Start Suction sampler Jar 1 mussels
24/07/2023	22:41	South Crystal	N 37 17.430	W 032 16.940	1718	Suction sampler broken
24/07/2023	22:46	South Crystal	N 37 17.434	W 032 16.932	1718	Direction Sapin
24/07/2023	22:52	Sapin	N 37 17.429	W 032 16.936	1719	Sampling mussels in PBT2
24/07/2023	22:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.432	W 032 16.933	1718	Start transit towards Cypres
24/07/2023	23:02	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.871	1732	Arrival at cypress
24/07/2023	23:10	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.866	1737	Measurement temperature = 302°C
24/07/2023	23:15	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti2 M23FLU63
24/07/2023	23:19	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti3 M23FLU64
24/07/2023	23:23	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.865	1737	Ti4 M23FLU65
24/07/2023	23:27	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti1 M23FLU66
24/07/2023	23:32	Lucky strike	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.874	1731	Start OTUS Western sites label 200
25/07/2023	05:09	Lucky strike	N 37 17.500	W 032 16.888	1733	End of profile
25/07/2023	05:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17.486	W 032 16.897	1734	transit towards Pico
25/07/2023	05:20	Lucky strike	N 37 17.452	W 032 16.912	1724	Arrival at Crystal

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
25/07/2023	05:23	Lucky strike	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.927	1718	Snowman
25/07/2023	05:42	Seamon W	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.792	1736	Arrival at Seamon W
25/07/2023	06:22	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.783	1738	Displacement buoyancy device cut and released
25/07/2023	06:52	Seamon W	N 37 17.427	W 032 16.820	1724	Device onboard
25/07/2023	07:13	Seamon W	N 37 17.477	W 032 16.792	1739	Start deploying OBS
25/07/2023	07:20	Seamon W	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.790	1739	Sismo in position
25/07/2023	07:28	Seamon W	N 37 17.434	W 032 16.789	1722	Departure from the bottom

7.9.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	21:11	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.784	1737	Station Seamon W in place
24/07/2023	22:11	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.788	1738	Installing cylindre SMASH
25/07/2023	07:20	Seamon W	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.790	1739	Sismo in position

7.9.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	21:22	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.786	1736	Triggering Niskin
24/07/2023	22:40	South Crystal	N 37 17.430	W 032 16.939	1718	Start Suction sampler Jar 1 mussels
24/07/2023	22:52	Sapin	N 37 17.429	W 032 16.936	1719	Sampling mussels in PBT2
24/07/2023	23:15	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti2 M23FLU63
24/07/2023	23:19	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti3 M23FLU64
24/07/2023	23:23	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.865	1737	Ti4 M23FLU65
24/07/2023	23:27	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti1 M23FLU66

7.9.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	23:10	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.866	1737	Measurement temperature = 302°C

7.9.6. OTUS

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
24/07/2023	23:32	Lucky strike	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.874	1731	Start OTUS Western sites label 200
25/07/2023	05:09	Lucky strike	N 37 17.500	W 032 16.888	1733	End of profile

7.9.7. Navigation

7.10. MoMARSAT 2023 DIVE 848-10

July, Tuesday 25 th

Victor launching position Seamon E	37°17.3181 N	32°16.5016 W	
Position Seamon E	37°17.3215 N	32°16.556 W	target
Launching time	22:37	Arrival at the bottom	
Departure from bottom	Thursday July, 27	Time Victor on board	

7.10.1. Objectives

Deployment probe Cypres, recovery SMASH, gaz tights Tour Eiffel, plume experiment Tour Eiffel, Suction sampler shrimp & crabs, OTUS Isabel, White Castle and geological exploration of escarpments, and distribution of corals/sponges towards the northern sites

Coordinates:

Seamon E	37°17.3238N	32°16.5528 W		
----------	-------------	--------------	--	--

Victor

Descending basket

	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	PBT2
1 HTNke	WIFI		

Ascending basket

Bag SMASH	4 Gaz tights	Niskin	PBT2
	WIFI		

Instrumentation

		SUCTION SAMPLER	
--	--	-----------------	--

7.10.2. Operations summary:

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	24:18	Seamon E	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.562	1698	Arrival at Seamon East
26/07/2023	24:26	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.559	1701	Remove grit bags
26/07/2023	24:34	Seamon E	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.556	1701	Dead weight released
26/07/2023	24:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1691	Final position of the station
26/07/2023	01:03	Seamon E	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.536	1681	TEMPO turned on
26/07/2023	01:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.536	1695	grit bag taken in the BASKET
26/07/2023	01:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1694	Trigger Niskin Seamon E
26/07/2023	01:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.551	1697	Direction station hydro
26/07/2023	02:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.544	1693	Towards Tour Eiffel
26/07/2023	02:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.531	1681	Measurement temperature =315°C
26/07/2023	02:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.532	1681	Ti8 M23FLU67
26/07/2023	02:54	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.531	1681	Ti7 M23FLU68
26/07/2023	03:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.530	1681	Ti6 M23FLU69
26/07/2023	03:08	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.530	1681	Ti5 M23FLU70
26/07/2023	03:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.529	1675	Towards Cyprès
26/07/2023	03:36	Cypres	N 37 17.448	W 032 16.855	1733	Arrival at Cyprès
26/07/2023	04:02	Cypres	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.865	1738	HTNKE 29016 installed
26/07/2023	04:07	Cypres	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.868	1736	towards South Crystal
26/07/2023	04:20	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	1718	Arrival at SouthCrystal
26/07/2023	04:30	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	jar1 Suction sampler
26/07/2023	04:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	Jar n°2 shrimp
26/07/2023	05:02	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.937	1719	Suction sampler gastropods jar 3
26/07/2023	05:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.936	1717	Transit SEAMON W
26/07/2023	05:13	Seamon W	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.792	1735	Arrival at Seamon W
26/07/2023	05:17	Seamon W	N 37 17.477	W 032 16.783	1739	DisplacementTCM 3-2
26/07/2023	05:19	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.793	1739	TCM 3-2 installed
26/07/2023	05:23	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.787	1738	All bags smash are tangled
26/07/2023	05:28	Seamon W	N 37 17.476	W 032 16.785	1739	Rope cut
26/07/2023	05:32	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.785	1739	Bag SMASH 3 in BASKET
26/07/2023	05:41	Lucky strike	N 37 17.470	W 032 16.794	1738	transit White Castle
26/07/2023	06:01	White Castle	N 37 17.362	W 032 16.872	1694	Start OTUS White castle
26/07/2023	06:25	White Castle	N 37 17.390	W 032 16.868	1715	End OTUS White castle
26/07/2023	06:25	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.397	W 032 16.865	1714	transit Tour Eiffel
26/07/2023	06:44	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.584	1689	Arrival at Hydro 2
26/07/2023	06:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.555	1702	Cable Hydro under dead weight
26/07/2023	07:02	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.559	1702	Cable under weight
26/07/2023	07:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.312	W 032 16.543	1699	Towards station
26/07/2023	07:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1692	Buoyancy device cut
26/07/2023	07:44	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.482	1671	Buoyancy device at the surface
26/07/2023	08:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.507	1679	Released at 07h28 and urface at 7h44

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	08:11	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.533	1693	Seamon Est caillebotis TEMPO : preparatino for TEMPO deloyment
26/07/2023	08:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.536	1693	Cable will be uncoiled at 250°
26/07/2023	08:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.534	1692	Caillebotis TEMPO
26/07/2023	08:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.537	1695	Opening arms
26/07/2023	08:29	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.537	1695	Projecteurs opened
26/07/2023	08:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1695	Start moving TEMPO
26/07/2023	09:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.536	1694	TEMPO in place
26/07/2023	09:07	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.536	1695	Stick WIFI in place
26/07/2023	09:09	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.535	1695	Seamon communicates
26/07/2023	09:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.535	1695	Lumière du ROV coupé
26/07/2023	09:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.536	1695	TEMPO vu de la station SEAMON est
26/07/2023	10:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.536	1695	Hydroctopus Connected
26/07/2023	10:02	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.537	1694	TEMPO turned on
26/07/2023	10:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.540	1695	module wifi in place
26/07/2023	10:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1695	Validation video FOV TEMPO
26/07/2023	10:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.311	W 032 16.553	1700	TCM3-D in place
26/07/2023	10:57	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.544	1687	Installing TCM3-A at the north of probes and colonisers TE nord
26/07/2023	11:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.534	1682	temperature to start plume experiment smokers
26/07/2023	11:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.533	1680	End plume experiment in smoker
26/07/2023	11:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.529	1683	Start Measurement of smoker with ruler
26/07/2023	12:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1683	Measurements laser
26/07/2023	12:02	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1683	Recording smoker sequence fumeur
26/07/2023	12:05	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1683	Grabing sediment to put it in the plume
26/07/2023	12:07	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1683	Dust released
26/07/2023	12:08	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.532	1683	Trying calcine squirt bottle
26/07/2023	12:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1683	Oil going out
26/07/2023	12:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.530	1683	Preparing OTUS box Isabel - Tour Eiffel-Cimendef
26/07/2023	12:30	Lucky strike	N 37 17.297	W 032 16.526	1695	Towards beginning of OTUS profile
26/07/2023	12:37	Lucky strike	N 37 17.264	W 032 16.561	1693	Start acquisition with OTUS
26/07/2023	13:45	Lucky strike	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.554	-100	Departure from bottom - black-out since 13:32

7.10.3. Moorings

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	24:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1691	Final position SEAMON E
26/07/2023	04:02	Cypres	N 37 17.445	W 032 16.865	1738	HTNKE 29016 installed
26/07/2023	05:19	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.793	1739	TCM 3-2 installed
26/07/2023	05:32	Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.785	1739	Bag SMASH 3 in BASKET
26/07/2023	09:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.536	1694	TEMPO in place
26/07/2023	10:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.311	W 032 16.553	1700	TCM3-D in place
26/07/2023	10:57	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.544	1687	Installing TCM3-A

7.10.4. Samples

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	01:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1694	Trigger Niskin Seamon E
26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU67
26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU68
26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU69
26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU70
26/07/2023	04:30	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	jar1 Suction sampler
26/07/2023	04:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	Jar n°2 Shrimp
26/07/2023	05:02	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.937	1719	Suction sampler Gastropods jar 3

7.10.5. Measurements

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	02:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.531	1681	Measurement temperature =315°C
26/07/2023	11:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.534	1682	temperature plume experiment Cyprien Fumeur.

7.10.6. OTUS

Date	Time	Locality	Latitude	Longitude	Dep(m)	Comment
26/07/2023	06:01	White Castle	N 37 17.362	W 032 16.872	1694	Start OTUS White castle
26/07/2023	06:25	White Castle	N 37 17.390	W 032 16.868	1715	End OTUS White castle
26/07/2023	12:37	Sites est	N 37 17.264	W 032 16.561	1693	Start acquisition OTUS
26/07/2023	13:45	Sites est	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.554	-100	Departure from bottom - black-out since 13:32

7.10.7. Navigation

8. Operations

8.1. Operations and surface moorings

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Equipment	Comment	Correspondant
12/07/2023	19:10:40	N 37 16.835	W 032 14.491	Ship	Arrival on site	
12/07/2023	19:15:00	N 37 16.825	W 032 14.487	Autonomous OBS	Release OBS : LSVEP	S. Besançon
12/07/2023	20:34:00	N 37 16.775	W 032 14.327	Autonomous OBS	OBS at the surface : LSVEP	S. Besançon
12/07/2023	21:48:00	N 37 16.851	W 032 14.525	Autonomous OBS	Mooring with winch Bathy : LSVEQ	S. Besançon
13/07/2023	00:40:00	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.327	Autonomous OBS	Winch Bathy on board	S. Besançon
13/07/2023	01:25:00	N 37 17.374	W 032 16.499	Buoyancy device SEAMON W	Mooring with deep cable	L. Gautier
14/07/2023	09:00:10	N 37 17.397	W 032 17.098	SEAMON W	Seamon W at the surface	L. Gautier
14/07/2023	10:24:40	N 37 17.149	W 032 16.409	SEAMON W	SEAMONW & Buoyancy device on board	L. Gautier
14/07/2023	14:48:40	N 37 17.050	W 032 16.888	Buoyancy device Seamon E	Mooring recovery device N37°17,319 - W32°16,558	L. Gautier
15/07/2023	09:25:00			BOREL	Release BOREL buoy	L. Gautier
15/07/2023	09:41:00			BOREL	Fixation BOREL	L. Gautier
15/07/2023	10:30:00			BOREL	Bouee BOREL on board	L. Gautier
15/07/2023	15:00:40	N 37 17.125	W 032 16.627	SEAMON E	SEAMON E at the surface	
15/07/2023	16:15:20	N 37 16.554	W 032 15.257	SEAMON E	SEAMON E & Buoyancy device on board :	
17/07/2023	15:11:00			Autonomous OBS	Release OBS : LSVWP	S. Besançon
17/07/2023	16:20:40	N 37 18.166	W 032 19.580	Autonomous OBS	OBS at the surface : LSVWP	S. Besançon
17/07/2023	17:19:30	N 37 18.109	W 032 16.759	Oceanographic mooring	Release oceanographic mooring	C. Lemaréchal
17/07/2023	17:32:40	N 37 18.094	W 032 16.713	Oceanographic mooring	Mooring at the surface	C. Lemaréchal
17/07/2023	20:00:00			Oceanographic mooring	Mouillage on board	C. Lemaréchal
17/07/2023	20:44:10	N 37 17.948	W 032 19.544	Autonomous OBS	Mooring par winch Bathy : LSVWQ	S. Besançon
17/07/2023	23:15:30	N 37 18.138	W 032 19.360	Autonomous OBS	Winch Bathy on board	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	03:06:10	N 37 15.924	W 032 18.022	Autonomous OBS	Release OBS : LSVSP	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	04:50:10	N 37 15.692	W 032 17.806	Autonomous OBS	OBS on board	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	05:27:40	N 37 15.628	W 032 17.865	Autonomous OBS	Mooring LSVSQ	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	08:40:10	N 37 15.620	W 032 17.858	Autonomous OBS	Winch bathy on board	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	09:42:00			Autonomous OBS	OBS LSVNP released	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	11:10:20	N 37 19.059	W 032 17.068	Autonomous OBS	OBS on board	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	11:35:10	N 37 19.150	W 032 16.852	Autonomous OBS	Mooring LSVNQ Winch bathy	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	13:40:10	N 37 19.150	W 032 16.838	Autonomous OBS	Winch bathy on board	S. Besançon
18/07/2023	14:33:10	N 37 17.756	W 032 16.735	bathymetric sounder	Mooring CTD bathymetric sounder	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	14:53:50	N 37 17.756	W 032 16.735	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder zt the bottom : 600 m	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	15:31:50	N 37 17.761	W 032 16.727	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder SEABIRD 19+ on board	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	15:36:20	N 37 17.762	W 032 16.727	bathymetric sounder	Mooring bathymetric sounder	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	16:12:00	N 37 17.763	W 032 16.728	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder At the bottom : 1600 m	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	17:02:00	N 37 17.763	W 032 16.728	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder SEABIRD 19+ on board	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	17:54:20	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.538	bathymetric sounder	Mooring bathymetric sounder	C. Lemaréchal
18/07/2023	23:56:10	N 37 17.425	W 032 16.622	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder SEABIRD 19+ on board	C. Lemaréchal
22/07/2023	11:00:20	N 37 16.966	W 032 16.507	SEAMON E	Mooring SEAMON E with deep cable	L. Gautier
22/07/2023	13:51:30	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.537	SEAMON E	Release SEAMON E	L. Gautier
22/07/2023	15:07:10	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.532	SEAMON E	SEAMON Est - Cable GF on board :	L. Gautier
23/07/2023	07:51:50	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.614	Buoyancy device SEAMON E	Release Buoyancy displacement device	L. Gautier
23/07/2023	08:22:10	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.647	Buoyancy device SEAMON E	Buoyancy device on board	L. Gautier
23/07/2023	11:34:40	N 37 16.998	W 032 16.934	Buoyancy device SEAMON E	Mooring with deep cable	L. Gautier
24/07/2023	10:10:40	N 37 16.831	W 032 16.614	SEAMON E	SEAMON E at the surface	L. Gautier
24/07/2023	11:32:20	N 37 17.731	W 032 16.494	SEAMON E	SEAMON E & Buoyancy device on board	L. Gautier
24/07/2023	14:28:00	N 37 17.205	W 032 16.992	SEAMON W	Mooring SEAMON W with deep cable	L. Gautier
24/07/2023	18:30:50	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.807	SEAMON W	Cable GF on board	L. Gautier

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Equipment	Comment	Correspondant
25/07/2023	06:50:10	N 37 17.587	W 032 16.924	Buoyancy device SEAMON W	Buoyancy device SEAMON W on board	L. Gautier
25/07/2023	10:23:30	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.527	bathymetric sounder	Start bathymetric sounders	C. Lemaréchal
25/07/2023	14:40:50	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.529	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder At the bottom : 1660 m	C. Lemaréchal
25/07/2023	15:51:20	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.527	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder at the surface	C. Lemaréchal
25/07/2023	16:10:40	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.527	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder on board	C. Lemaréchal
25/07/2023	17:10:10	N 37 16.947	W 032 16.234	SEAMON E	Mooring SEAMON E par TGF	L. Gautier
25/07/2023	21:49:30	N 37 17.370	W 032 16.577	SEAMON E	Cable GF on board	L. Gautier
26/07/2023	08:00:30	N 37 17.372	W 032 16.442	Buoyancy device SEAMON E	Buoyancy device SEAMON E on board	L. Gautier
26/07/2023	17:04:10	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.540	bathymetric sounder	Mooring Bathymetric sounder	C. Lemaréchal
26/07/2023	23:10:40	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.528	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder SEABIRD 19+ At the bottom	C. Lemaréchal
27/07/2023	01:00:10	N 37 17.463	W 032 16.620	bathymetric sounder	Bathymetric sounder SEABIRD 19+ on board	C. Lemaréchal

8.2. CTD casts

Correspondant C. Lemaréchal, UBO-LOPS

Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	Device	Observation
18/07/2023	14:33:10	N 37 17.756	W 032 16.735	600	SEABIRD 19+	Intercalibration mooring
18/07/2023	16:12:00	N 37 17.763	W 032 16.728	1600	SEABIRD 19+	Intercalibration mooring
18/07/2023	17:54:20	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.538	1660	SEABIRD 19+	Plume experiment Tour Eiffel
25/07/2023	10:23:30	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.527	1660	SEABIRD 19+	Plume experiment Tour Eiffel
26/07/2023	17:04:10	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.540	1660	SEABIRD 19+	Plume experiment Tour Eiffel

8.3. Moorings recovered or installed during the cruise with the ROV VICTOR

NOM	Date de pose	PL (pose)	Date récup.	PL (récup.)	Site	Latitude	Longitude	Correspondant
Biolucky	24/06/2022	2041-14	13/07/2023	839-1	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	C. Rommevaux
BT11	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.537	M. Matabos
BT12	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.535	M. Matabos
BT13	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.530	M. Matabos
cage G12/G24	16/07/2023	842-4			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.533	M. Matabos
cage M12/M24	16/07/2023	842-4			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.543	M. Matabos
cage M36	16/07/2023	842-4			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.547	M. Matabos
Cylindre SMASH	24/07/2023	847-9			Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.788	P. Davies
DEAFS	24/06/2022	2041-14	13/07/2023	839-1	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.546	V. Chavagnac
HTNKE29006	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Tour Eiffel (est)	37.288727	-32.27538	M. Cannat
HTNKE29008	13/06/2021	2005-17	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.540	M. Cannat
HTNKE29008	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.540	M. Cannat
HTNKE29009	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.522	M. Cannat
HTNKE29014	20/07/2023	844-6			Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
HTNKE29016	15/06/2022	2032-5	14/07/2023	839-1	Montsegur (nord)	37.28825	-32.27558	M. Cannat
HTNKE29016	26/07/2023	848-10			Cypres	N 37 17.456	W 032 16.848	M. Cannat
HTNKE29017	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	White Castle	N 37 17.3927	W 032 16.861	M. Cannat
HTNKE29020	12/06/2022	2030-3	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (nord)	37.289067	-32.27555	M. Cannat
HTNKE30001	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.540	M. Cannat
HTNKE30002	21/06/2022	2038-11	17/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (sud)		-32.27576	M. Cannat
HTNKE30002	17/07/2023	842-4			White Castle	N 37 17.388	W 032 16.869	M. Cannat
HTNKE30007	22/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.540	M. Cannat
HTNKE30011	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	South Crystal	37.29059	-32.28217	M. Cannat
HTNKE30012	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	White Castle	N 37 17.3927	W 032 16.861	M. Cannat
HTNKE30012	20/07/2023	844-6			Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.525	M. Cannat
HTNKE30015	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.533	M. Cannat
HTNKE38001	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/07/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (Soleil)	37.27578	-32.28885	M. Cannat
HTNKE38003	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel	37.288955	-32.27555	M. Cannat
HTNKE 41001	17/06/2022	2034-7	20/07/2023	844-6	Sintra	37.29211	-32.27510	M. Cannat
HTNKE 41001	23/07/2023	846-8			White Castle	N 37 17.389	W 032 16.861	M. Cannat
HTNKE41002	21/06/2022	2038-11	14/07/2023	839-1	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.525	M. Cannat
HTNKE41003	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/07/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (sud)	37.28882	-32.27555	M. Cannat
HTNKE41003	22/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
HTW005	16/06/2022	2033-6	17/07/2023	842-4	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.867	M. Cannat
HTW005	23/07/2023	846-8			White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.867	M. Cannat

HTWN013	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	White Castle	N37 17.282	W 032 16.536'	M. Cannat
HTWN019	19/06/2022	2036-9	13/07/2023	839-1	Montsegur	N37 17.282	W 032 16.536'	M. Cannat
HTWN019	14/07/2023	840-2			ALSICS	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	M. Cannat
HTWN021	19/06/2022	2029-2	14/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel sud	37.27551	-32.28892	M. Cannat
HTWN021	24/07/2023	846-8			Montsegur	37.2879786	-32.2756538	M. Cannat
LSCAP-6	21/07/2023	844-6			Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.834	C. Rommevaux
LSCAP-5	02/06/2021	1996-8	21/07/2023	844-6	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	C. Rommevaux
LSLL-2 FeOx	20/07/2023	844-6			Lac de lave	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	C. Rommevaux
LSLL1	08/06/2021	2000-12	20/07/2023	844-6	Lac de lave	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.795	C. Rommevaux
LSSW1	23/07/2023	845-5			Sintra	N 37 17.544	W 032 16.491	C. Rommevaux
LSTE9	11/06/2021	2003-15	14/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.529	C. Rommevaux
LSNTE1	16/07/2023	841-3			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.540	C. Rommevaux
LSY3-01	17/07/2023	842-3			Y3	37.2919	-32.27783	C. Rommevaux
LTgrad1	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/07/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (sud)	37.28882	-32.27574	M. Cannat
LTgrad1	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.528	M. Cannat
LTgrad2	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (west)	37.289013	-32.27549	M. Cannat
LTgrad2	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.515	M. Cannat
LTgrad3	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.522	M. Cannat
LTgrad5	17/07/2023	842-4			White Castle	N 37 17.402	W 032 16.867	M. Cannat
LTgrad6	12/06/2022	2030-3	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (nord)	37.289067	-32.27555	M. Cannat
LTgrad6	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.511	M. Cannat
LTgrad8	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	White Castle	N 37 17.3927	W 032 16.861	M. Cannat
LTgrad8	22/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.539	M. Cannat
LTgrad9	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/07/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel	37.289067	-32.27555	M. Cannat
LTgrad9	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.574	M. Cannat
LTgrad10	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (west)	37.288963	-32.27579	M. Cannat
LTgrad10	20/07/2023	844-6			Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.514	M. Cannat
LTgrad12	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Tour Eiffel (est)	37.289013	-32.27549	M. Cannat
LTgrad14	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Tour Eiffel (est)	37.288727	-32.27538	M. Cannat
LTgrad15	15/07/2023	840-2			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
LTgrad20	22/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.528	M. Cannat
LTgrad21	22/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.544	M. Cannat
LTi1	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Tour Eiffel (est)	37.28901	-32.2754635.0	M. Cannat
LTi1	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
LTMetal3	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Point triple des Azores	37.288848	-32.27531	M. Cannat
LTMetal11	24/06/2022	2041-14	20/07/2023	844-6	Point triple des Azores	37.288888	-32.27528	M. Cannat
LTMetal12	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/04/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (sud)	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
LTMetal13	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/04/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (sud)	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat
LTMetal14	16/06/2022	2033-6	13/04/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel (sud)	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.546	M. Cannat

LTW003	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (west)	37.28905	-32.27579	M. Cannat
LTW003	17/07/2023	842-4			South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.932	M. Cannat
LTW006	12/06/2022	2030-3	17/07/2023	842-4	South Crystal	37.29057	-32.28209	M. Cannat
LTW017	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel (sud)	N 37 17.3403	W 032 16.522	M. Cannat
LTW017	20/07/2023	844-6			Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.524	M. Cannat
LTW018	17/07/2023	842-4			South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.934	M. Cannat
LTW020	21/06/2022	2038-11	22/07/2023	845-7	Tour Eiffel (west)	37.289015	-32.27586	M. Cannat
SEAMON_EST	26/07/2023	848-10			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	L. Gautier
SEAMON_EST	23/06/2022	2040-13	14/07/2023	840-2	Point triple des Azores	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.531	L. Gautier
SEAMON_W	24/07/2023	847-9			Lucky strike	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.784	L. Gautier
SEAMON_W	20/06/2022	2037-10	13/07/2023	839-1	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.788	L. Gautier
SMASH (poches)	26/07/2023	847-9			Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.785	P. Davies
Sismo_SEAMON_W	25/07/2023	847-9			Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.788	S. Besançon
TCM3-1	21/06/2022	2038-11	16/07/2023	842-4	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.541	M. Cannat
TCM3-2	26/07/2023	848-10			Seamon W	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.793	M. Cannat
TCM3-2	21/06/2022	2038-11	20/07/2023	844-6	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.789	M. Cannat
TCM3-3	16/06/2022	2033-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.533	M. Cannat
TCM3-A	12/06/2021	2004-16	22/07/2023	845-7	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.533	M. Matabos
TCM3-A	26/07/2023	848-10			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.361	W 032 16.544	M. Matabos
TCM3-B	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.533	M. Matabos
TCM3-B	20/07/2023	844-6			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.540	M. Matabos
TCM3-C			15/07/2023	840-2	Lucky strike	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.540	M. Matabos
TCM3-C	20/07/2023	844-6			Lucky strike	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.533	M. Matabos
TCM3-D	21/06/2022	2038-11	15/07/2023	840-2	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.505	M. Matabos
TCM3-D	26/07/2023	848-10			Lucky strike	N 37 17.311	W 032 16.553	M. Matabos
TEMPO	27/06/2019	1953-15	13/07/2023	839-1	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	J. Sarrazin
TEMPO	26/07/2023	848			Lucky strike	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.536	J. Sarrazin

8.4. Liste des prélèvements

8.4.1. Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS)

Autorisation REGIÃO AUTÓNOMA DOS AÇORES

Vice-Presidência do Governo dos Açores

Direção Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia

Contacts : Fabio AL. Vieira (Fabio.AL.Vieira@azores.gov.pt), Ana Pascoal (Ana.CT.Pascoal@azores.gov.pt), scientific.samples@azores.gov.pt

CCIR-RAA/2023/35

Addendum envoyé le 18/07/2023

8.4.2. Biological sampling

PL	Date	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
839-1	13/07/2023	23:42	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.540	1690	Sampling mussels in PBT2
839-1	14/07/2023	01:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.527	1700	Suction 2, gastropods
839-1	14/07/2023	01:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	Suction 3, gastropods
840-2	15/07/2023	05:35	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1676	Suction jar 1
840-2	15/07/2023	05:38	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction jar 2
840-2	15/07/2023	05:39	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction jar 3
840-2	15/07/2023	05:40	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Suction jar 4
842-4	16/07/2023	13:28	Nord TE	N 37 17.354	W 032 16.528	1689	Sampling Bag PEP 16 NTE Filtered
842-4	16/07/2023	13:32	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.539	1690	Sampling Bag PEP 17 NTE Non filtered
842-4	16/07/2023	13:49	Nord TE	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.533	1690	Sampling Tapis M23FeOx-NTE PBT1
842-4	16/07/2023	16:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.530	1701	sampling C2a in PBT2
842-4	16/07/2023	16:27	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.531	1701	Suction 1 & 2 in C2a
842-4	16/07/2023	17:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.527	1701	sampling C1b in PBT3
842-4	16/07/2023	17:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.528	1701	Suction 3 bacterial mats C1b
842-4	16/07/2023	21:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.541	1700	Sampling fauna on quadrat C1a in PBT4
842-4	16/07/2023	21:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction4 on quadrat C1a
842-4	16/07/2023	21:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction 5 on quadrat C1a
842-4	16/07/2023	22:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1699	Sampling claw fauna quadrat C2b in PBT5.
842-4	16/07/2023	22:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1700	Start Suction 6 on quadrat C2b
842-4	16/07/2023	22:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.532	1700	Start Suction 7 on quadrat C2b
842-4	17/07/2023	08:15	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.541	1693	Sampling mussels sulphide area PBT2
842-4	17/07/2023	08:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Suction 8 SPIDER
842-4	17/07/2023	09:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.546	1693	Sampling large mussels in PBT3
844-6	20/07/2023	01:11	Lac de lave	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Start Sampling PEP Bag 14 M23-LL-PEP
844-6	20/07/2023	01:15	Lac de lave	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.794	1738	Start de Sampling PEP bag 15 M23-LL-PEP
844-6	20/07/2023	01:32	Lac de lave	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.796	1738	Sampling iron mat M23-LLFeOx
844-6	20/07/2023	02:05	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.790	1733	Sampling Niskin
844-6	20/07/2023	06:04	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.670	1727	Sampling mussels in PBT3
844-6	20/07/2023	06:21	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1727	Suction gastropods SUCTION1
844-6	21/07/2023	13:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.834	1669	Sampling M23-Cap-FeOx PBT4
844-6	21/07/2023	18:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1668	Start sampling mussels PBT2
844-6	21/07/2023	19:19	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1659	Sampling chimney in PBT1 M23-CapChem
844-6	22/07/2023	04:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.540	1693	Sampling quadrat référence PBT3
845-7	22/07/2023	22:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.545	1692	Suction 1 on reference quadrat area SPIDER
845-7	22/07/2023	23:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1700	Suction 2 C1a-cg
845-7	23/07/2023	01:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.535	1700	C1 Bcg SUCTION3
845-7	23/07/2023	02:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.533	1700	Suction4 in C2bcg
845-7	23/07/2023	03:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.532	1698	SUCTION 5 in center C2acg
845-7	23/07/2023	03:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.533	1698	C2a-ag in PBT2
845-7	23/07/2023	03:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.520	1701	Suction 6 in center P1
845-7	23/07/2023	04:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.535	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
845-7	23/07/2023	05:33	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Start Sampling PEP 12 T= 4.60°C

PL	Date	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
845-7	23/07/2023	05:35	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Sampling SUCTION Jar 7 in the center I1
845-7	23/07/2023	05:46	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling SUCTION 8 I2
845-7	23/07/2023	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.541	W 032 16.487	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-WSF Bag 18 non filtered
845-7	23/07/2023	07:02	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.539	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-PEP-SWF Bag 19 filtered
845-7	23/07/2023	07:15	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.540	W 032 16.488	1619	Sampling M23-WS-FeOx
846-8	23/07/2023	23:35	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.671	1727	M23-PEP-Y3 Bag 19 4.56°C
846-8	23/07/2023	23:45	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.673	1727	M23-PEP-Y3 FeOx Bag 18 NF 3 min
846-8	23/07/2023	23:57	Y3 FeOx	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.670	1727	M23-Y3-FeOx PBT1
846-8	24/07/2023	24:49	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.538	1687	Sampling mussels in PBT2
846-8	24/07/2023	03:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.533	1700	Sampling mussels PBT3
846-8	24/07/2023	04:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1701	shrimp SUCTION 1 & 2
846-8	24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction zone gastropods, Suction 3
846-8	24/07/2023	06:40	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	Suction jar 4, zone mussels
846-8	24/07/2023	06:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.272	W 032 16.569	1697	Suction jar 5
847-9	24/07/2023	22:40	South Crystal	N 37 17.430	W 032 16.939	1718	Start Suction Jar 1 mussels
847-9	24/07/2023	22:52	Sapin	N 37 17.429	W 032 16.936	1719	Sampling mussels in PBT2
848-10	26/07/2023	04:30	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	jar1 Suction
848-10	26/07/2023	04:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.935	1719	Jar n°2 Shrimp
848-10	26/07/2023	05:02	South Crystal	N 37 17.436	W 032 16.937	1719	Suction Gastropods jar 3

8.4.3. Fluid sampling

PL	Date	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
839-1	13/07/2023	09:15	Seamon W	N 37 17.470	W 032 16.788	1735	Trigger Niskin
839-1	13/07/2023	10:16	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.792	1738	Prise d'un morceau de basalte
839-1	13/07/2023	12:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.542	1699	Ti1 M23FLU01
839-1	13/07/2023	13:00	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.541	1699	Ti2 M23FLU02
839-1	13/07/2023	13:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.541	1699	Ti3 M23FLU03
839-1	13/07/2023	13:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1699	Ti4 M23FLU04
839-1	13/07/2023	17:41	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.536	1698	Ti5 M23FLU05
839-1	13/07/2023	17:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.537	1698	Ti8 M23FLU06
839-1	13/07/2023	17:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.537	1698	Ti7 M23FLU07
839-1	14/07/2023	02:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1700	start pep 3 (sea water temp)
840-2	14/07/2023	20:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17.408	W 032 16.591	936	PEP 4 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.409	W 032 16.587	958	PEP 5 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.411	W 032 16.580	990	PEP6 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:36	Lucky strike	N 37 17.413	W 032 16.573	1012	PEP7 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.564	1037	PEP8 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.559	1060	PEP9 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	20:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.417	W 032 16.556	1082	PEP10 triggered
840-2	14/07/2023	21:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1691	Trigger Niskin
840-2	14/07/2023	22:18	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.534	1688	Ti5 M23FLU08
840-2	14/07/2023	22:22	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti6 M23FLU09
840-2	14/07/2023	22:26	Aisics	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.532	1688	Ti7 M23FLU10
840-2	14/07/2023	22:30	Aisics	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.531	1688	Ti8 M23FLU11
840-2	15/07/2023	05:03	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti1 M23FLU12
840-2	15/07/2023	05:12	Isabel	N 37 17.394	W 032 16.639	1677	Ti2 M23FLU13
840-2	15/07/2023	05:19	Isabel	N 37 17.395	W 032 16.641	1677	Ti3 M23FLU14
841-3	15/07/2023	23:28	TE Nord	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.538	1690	Ti1 M23FLU15
841-3	15/07/2023	23:35	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.541	1690	Ti2 M23FLU16
841-3	15/07/2023	23:41	TE Nord	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.536	1690	Ti3 M23FLU17
841-3	15/07/2023	23:45	TE Nord	N 37 17.352	W 032 16.540	1690	Ti4 M23FLU18
842-4	16/07/2023	14:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti1 M23FLU19
842-4	16/07/2023	15:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.534	1699	Ti2 M23FLU20
842-4	16/07/2023	15:08	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.534	1699	Ti2 M23FLU21

PL	Date	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
842-4	16/07/2023	15:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.535	1699	Ti4 M23FLU22
842-4	17/07/2023	01:00	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.933	1719	Ti8 M23FLU23
842-4	17/07/2023	01:06	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti7 M23FLU24
842-4	17/07/2023	01:11	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.934	1719	Ti6 M23FLU25
842-4	17/07/2023	01:22	South Crystal	N 37 17.438	W 032 16.935	1719	Ti5 M23FLU26
842-4	17/07/2023	11:12	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	M23-FLU27 diffuse
842-4	17/07/2023	11:22	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.670	1728	Sampling M23-FLU28 diffuse
842-4	17/07/2023	11:27	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.672	1728	Sampling M23-FLU29 diffuse
842-4	17/07/2023	11:32	Y3-FeOx	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.666	1728	Sampling M23-FLU30 diffuse
844-6	20/07/2023	02:05	Seamon W	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.790	1733	Sampling Niskin
844-6	20/07/2023	02:45	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.672	1725	Sampling Ti1 M23FLU31
844-6	20/07/2023	02:52	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.672	1726	Sampling Ti2 M23FLU32
844-6	20/07/2023	02:57	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti3 M23FLU33
844-6	20/07/2023	03:04	Y3	N 37 17.510	W 032 16.671	1725	Sampling Ti4 M23FLU34
844-6	20/07/2023	12:54	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti8 M23FLU35
844-6	20/07/2023	13:03	Sintra	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.500	1613	Ti7 M23FLU36
844-6	20/07/2023	13:09	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.501	1613	Ti6 M23FLU37
844-6	20/07/2023	13:14	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.502	1613	Ti5 M23FLU38
844-6	21/07/2023	12:29	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1669	Sampling M23-FLU39
844-6	21/07/2023	12:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU40
844-6	21/07/2023	13:00	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.832	1669	Sampling M23-FLU41
844-6	21/07/2023	13:15	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.831	1669	Sampling M23-FLU42
844-6	21/07/2023	19:48	Capelinhos	N 37 17.365	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti8 M23FLU43
844-6	21/07/2023	19:53	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1658	Ti5 M23FLU44
844-6	21/07/2023	20:01	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.832	1658	Ti7 M23FLU45
844-6	21/07/2023	20:06	Capelinhos	N 37 17.356	W 032 15.828	1658	Ti6 M23FLU46
845-7	22/07/2023	22:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.547	1692	PEP1 sur quadrat SPIDER reference
845-7	22/07/2023	23:25	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.540	1699	Start PEP 2 C1a - 4.68°C
845-7	22/07/2023	23:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.536	1700	PEP 3 C1a-cg, 4.5°C
845-7	23/07/2023	24:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.540	1698	M23FLU47
845-7	23/07/2023	01:04	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU48
845-7	23/07/2023	01:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU49
845-7	23/07/2023	01:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.539	1698	M23FLU50
845-7	23/07/2023	01:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 4 C1 bcg T= 7.60 - 6.87
845-7	23/07/2023	02:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.531	1700	PEP 5 in c2a T=4.76 -4.75
845-7	23/07/2023	02:16	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.534	1700	PEP 6 in R0 -CENTER T= 6.68 - 4.80
845-7	23/07/2023	02:22	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1700	PEP 7 C2bcg T= 4.78 - 4.80
845-7	23/07/2023	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.531	1699	Star PEP 8 in C1b
845-7	23/07/2023	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1698	Start PEP 9 in C2b
845-7	23/07/2023	03:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.519	1701	PEP 11 périphérie P1 T= 4.50
845-7	23/07/2023	05:33	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.547	1650	Start sampling PEP 12 T= 4.60°C
845-7	23/07/2023	05:43	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1650	Sampling PEP 13 T=4.55°C I2
845-7	23/07/2023	06:16	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.540	1640	Sampling M23-FLU51 TiCloche 8
845-7	23/07/2023	06:21	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU52 Ti Cloche 7
845-7	23/07/2023	06:26	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.537	1640	Sampling M23-FLU53 Ti Cloche 5
845-7	23/07/2023	06:31	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.539	1640	Sampling M23-FLU54 Ti Cloche 6
846-8	23/07/2023	21:49	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.869	1708	Ti5 M23FLU55
846-8	23/07/2023	21:54	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti6 M23FLU56
846-8	23/07/2023	22:01	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti7 M23FLU57
846-8	23/07/2023	22:07	White Castle	N 37 17.381	W 032 16.868	1708	Ti8 M23FLU58
846-8	24/07/2023	02:35	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti1 M23FLU59
846-8	24/07/2023	02:43	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti2 M23FLU60
846-8	24/07/2023	02:48	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.545	1697	Ti3 M23FLU61
846-8	24/07/2023	02:56	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.544	1697	Ti4 M23FLU62
847-9	24/07/2023	21:22	Seamon W	N 37 17.475	W 032 16.786	1736	Trigger Niskin
847-9	24/07/2023	23:15	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti2 M23FLU63
847-9	24/07/2023	23:19	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti3 M23FLU64
847-9	24/07/2023	23:23	Cypres	N 37 17.444	W 032 16.865	1737	Ti4 M23FLU65
847-9	24/07/2023	23:27	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.867	1737	Ti1 M23FLU66
848-10	26/07/2023	01:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.533	1694	Trigger Niskin Seamon E

PL	Date	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
848-10	26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU67
848-10	26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU68
848-10	26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU69
848-10	26/07/2023	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.343	1684	Ti1 M23FLU70

8.5. Continuous measurements

Equipent on VICTOR: Temperature, Optode

Date	PL	Heure	Localité	Latitude	Longitude	Prof(m)	Commentaire
13/07/2023	839-1	12:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.543	1699	measurement of T°C New DEAFS – 312°C
13/07/2023	839-1	16:12	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.542	1697	Measurement of Temperature – 315°C
13/07/2023	839-1	19:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	measurement T 1 on small mussels
13/07/2023	839-1	19:50	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 1 T 8.5 max
13/07/2023	839-1	19:51	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.543	1696	measurement 2 in grey 8.5
13/07/2023	839-1	19:52	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.543	1696	measurement 3 in grey pushed 5 cm max
13/07/2023	839-1	19:55	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	measurement 3 51.2
13/07/2023	839-1	19:56	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.544	1696	measurement 4 bacterial mat on red substrate 5.2
13/07/2023	839-1	19:58	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 5 substrate orange 10.86
13/07/2023	839-1	19:59	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 6 2 cm in substrate orange 13.4
13/07/2023	839-1	20:02	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 7 on hard substrate small mussels 5.2
13/07/2023	839-1	20:04	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 8 on substrate grey, small mussels & bacterial mats 8.9
13/07/2023	839-1	20:05	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 9 substrate grey, bacterial mats probe pushed au max
13/07/2023	839-1	20:06	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 9 60.7
13/07/2023	839-1	20:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 10 white smooth substrate (barite?) 7.9
13/07/2023	839-1	20:09	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 11 probe pushed white smooth substrate shimmering tres visible
13/07/2023	839-1	20:11	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 11 83.2
13/07/2023	839-1	20:12	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 12 on smooth grey substrate in white crust 33.6
13/07/2023	839-1	20:14	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 13 on bacterial mat
13/07/2023	839-1	20:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 13 5.6
13/07/2023	839-1	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 14 on average mussels
13/07/2023	839-1	20:16	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement
13/07/2023	839-1	20:17	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 14 5.25
13/07/2023	839-1	20:20	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 15 on substrate orange
13/07/2023	839-1	20:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 16 4.7
13/07/2023	839-1	20:22	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1696	measurement 17 pushed less than a 1 cm 6.98
13/07/2023	839-1	20:25	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 18 substrate grey 4.76
13/07/2023	839-1	20:26	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 19 pushed de ?? 5 cm? 15.5
13/07/2023	839-1	20:30	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 20
13/07/2023	839-1	20:32	Seamon E	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 20 on weird « sticks » 4.75
13/07/2023	839-1	20:35	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	measurement 21 on grey substrate near LTmetal 13
13/07/2023	839-1	20:36	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 21 5.07
13/07/2023	839-1	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement
13/07/2023	839-1	20:37	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1696	measurement 22 pushed 8 cm
13/07/2023	839-1	20:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.540	1696	measurement 22 42.5
14/07/2023	839-1	02:37	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.531	1700	C1a temperature 4.87 max
14/07/2023	839-1	02:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.529	1700	C2bcg temperature center
14/07/2023	839-1	02:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.528	1700	R0a Temperature 6.30
14/07/2023	839-1	03:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1700	C1bcg temperature 4.72

14/07/2023	839-1	03:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.534	1699	C1a temperature 4.95
14/07/2023	839-1	04:02	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.532	1698	C2b temperature 5.13
14/07/2023	839-1	04:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.530	1698	C2acg temperature 5.02
14/07/2023	839-1	04:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.532	1699	R1 Temperature 5.02
14/07/2023	840-2	22:08	Aisics	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.532	1688	T°C 305°C
15/07/2023	840-2	04:49	Isabel	N 37 17.396	W 032 16.636	1677	T à 293°C
15/07/2023	841-3	23:16	TE Nord	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.537	1690	T° mesured 55°C
16/07/2023	841-3	24:22	TE Nord	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.544	1689	measurement temperature on iron mat
16/07/2023	842-4	13:27	Nord TE	N 37 17.358	W 032 16.523	1689	Measurement Temperature 4,65°C
16/07/2023	842-4	14:42	Montsegur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.537	1699	measurement T° = 315°C
16/07/2023	842-4	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.530	1701	C2a temp: 4.60 - 4.76
16/07/2023	842-4	17:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.530	1701	C1b temperature top left 4.85
16/07/2023	842-4	20:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.542	1693	Measurement T°C 5.55°C-5.67
16/07/2023	842-4	21:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.539	1700	Probe PEP in place C1a 4.89°C, 4.96°C
16/07/2023	842-4	21:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.535	1699	Measurement temperature on C2b
17/07/2023	842-4	24:31	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.936	1719	measurement de T° = 324°C
17/07/2023	842-4	08:03	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.545	1693	Prise temperature probe 4 5.87
17/07/2023	842-4	08:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.533	1701	T°C coin low ROa, 11.80°C, 13.76, 15.73
20/07/2023	844-6	02:37	Y3	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.671	1725	Measurement temperature T=312°C
20/07/2023	844-6	12:48	Sintra	N 37 17.529	W 032 16.502	1613	Measurement temperature T° = 219°C
20/07/2023	844-6	15:27	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C left corner quadrat I1,T°C 4.55 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	844-6	15:32	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.545	1651	T°C right corner high I2, 4.57
20/07/2023	844-6	15:40	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.543	1651	T°C center on I2 4.57
20/07/2023	844-6	15:44	Sintra inactif	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.546	1651	T°C right corner high, quadrat I2 :4.57°C
20/07/2023	844-6	16:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1694	Prise de T°C left corner low reference quadrat SPIDER, 5.62-5.50,5.69 (probe 4)
20/07/2023	844-6	16:55	Lucky strike	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1694	T°C right corner high reference quadrat SPIDER 5.45°C, 5.42°C
20/07/2023	844-6	17:24	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.542	1694	Temperature reference quadrat left corner,6.60°C, 6.81, 7.00, 6.70°C
20/07/2023	844-6	17:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.543	1694	T°C right corner high reference quadrat SPIDER, 5.88°C, 6.01, 6.11°C
20/07/2023	844-6	22:53	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.515	1693	Measurement button 21 chaîne BT12 - 4.69°C
20/07/2023	844-6	22:54	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.531	1693	Measurement button 22 chaîne BT12 - 4.69°C
20/07/2023	844-6	22:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement button 23 chaîne BT12 - 4.61°C
20/07/2023	844-6	22:58	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement temperature button 24 chain BT12 - 4,61°C
20/07/2023	844-6	22:59	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature button 25 chain BT12- 4,55°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.532	1693	Measurement temperature 1st button chain BT11
20/07/2023	844-6	23:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.533	1693	Measurement temperature second button BT11
20/07/2023	844-6	23:12	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3rd button BT11 - 4.64°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement 4th button n°14 - 4.68°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.539	1693	Measurement button 5 n°15 chain BT1 - 4.66°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:20	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	1er button on BT13 - 5,31°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1693	Measurement temperature 2nd button on BT13 - 5,22°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 3rd button on BT13 - 6,54°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:25	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature 4th button on BT13 8°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.536	1693	Measurement 5th button on BT13 - 7,9°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:32	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.536	1693	6,7°C high mineralisation
20/07/2023	844-6	23:34	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1693	Measurement temperature smoker exit TEMPO area
20/07/2023	844-6	23:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement in focused exit - 42,5
20/07/2023	844-6	23:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.537	1693	Measurement diffusion zone- 28°C
20/07/2023	844-6	23:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.536	1693	Fmange at 30°C
21/07/2023	844-6	24:56	Périph MS	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.519	1702	T°C 4.46 (probe 4)
21/07/2023	844-6	01:00	Périph MS	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.517	1702	T°C 4.45°C (high right corner periphery)

							quadrat)
21/07/2023	844-6	01:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.553	1695	Measurements south MS (probe 4)
21/07/2023	844-6	12:08	Capelinhos	N 37 17.366	W 032 15.831	1669	Temperature iron mat
21/07/2023	844-6	19:41	Capelinhos	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.833	1659	temperature 307°C
22/07/2023	844-6	04:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.540	1693	T°C 5.18°C, 5.14°C, 5.26°C, 5.45 °C reference quadrat SPIDER
22/07/2023	844-6	04:18	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.541	1693	106°C max measured at the top of the reference quadrat
22/07/2023	844-6	05:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T1 4.71
22/07/2023	844-6	05:14	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T2 pushed 20°C
22/07/2023	844-6	05:19	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T3 at the surface grey/orange surface 4.62
22/07/2023	844-6	05:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T3 pushed 43°C
22/07/2023	844-6	05:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T5 on grey
22/07/2023	844-6	05:26	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.541	1697	Measurement T4 on light grey 6.44
22/07/2023	844-6	05:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T6 pushed 44°C
22/07/2023	844-6	05:36	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.540	1697	Measurement T7 on orange mat 5.05
22/07/2023	844-6	05:37	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.539	1697	Measurement T8 probe pushed on orange mat 41°C
22/07/2023	845-5	22:28	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.547	1692	Measurement T°C on reference quadrat SPIDER – max 6,82°C
23/07/2023	845-5	24:36	Montsegur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.538	1698	Measurement de T°: 312.8°C DEAFS
23/07/2023	845-5	06:00	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.538	1640	Measurement temperature 77°C
23/07/2023	845-5	06:59	Sintra FeOx	N 37 17.542	W 032 16.486	1619	T=4.60°C – LSSW1
23/07/2023	846-8	21:41	White Castle	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.868	1708	measurement temperature = 320°C
24/07/2023	846-8	01:00	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.538	1687	Start measurement temperature 1 probe 6 on COMBO - 6°C-6,4°C
24/07/2023	846-8	01:01	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.537	1687	Start measurement temperature 2 - 28°
24/07/2023	846-8	02:27	Sud TE soleil	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.545	1697	measurement temperature = 72°C
24/07/2023	846-8	05:42	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.565	1697	Measurement T°C max 108°C
24/07/2023	846-8	05:43	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.565	1697	Temperature near larges mussels 8.10°C
24/07/2023	846-8	05:45	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.64°C on average mussels
24/07/2023	846-8	05:46	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	4.61 on mat/mussels
24/07/2023	846-8	05:48	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.269	W 032 16.566	1697	4.75 on small mussels/gastropods
24/07/2023	846-8	05:56	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.566	1697	5.04 on gastropods
24/07/2023	846-8	06:10	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C 5.45 on mussels small/average
24/07/2023	846-8	06:12	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C on average mussels 5.63
24/07/2023	846-8	06:13	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C on gastropods 7.52
24/07/2023	846-8	06:14	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C white zone 9.69°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:15	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 7.15 small mussels
24/07/2023	846-8	06:16	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 6.26°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C average mussel 6.40°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:17	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C orange mat 10.53 °C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:19	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.567	1697	T°C small crack 24°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:22	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	Small fluide exit
24/07/2023	846-8	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	T°C 26.5°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:23	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.569	1697	Probe deeper T°C 61°C (2 cm)
24/07/2023	846-8	06:25	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.566	1697	T°C probe pushed 80.6°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:27	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	Larger mussels 6.21°C
24/07/2023	846-8	06:28	Sud Cimendef	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.568	1697	T°C larger mussels 5.0°C
24/07/2023	847-9	23:10	Cypres	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.866	1737	measurement temperature = 302°C
26/07/2023	848-10	02:39	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.339	W 032 16.531	1681	measurement temperature =315°C
26/07/2023	848-10	11:13	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.534	1682	temperature probe for plume experiment

9. Annexes

Authorization AMP/2023/007

<p>REGIÃO AVTÓNOMA DOS AÇORES SECRETARIA REGIONAL DO MAR E DAS PESCAS DIREÇÃO REGIONAL DE POLÍTICAS MARÍTIMAS</p>	<p style="font-size: 1.2em; font-weight: bold;">AMP / 2023 / 007</p> <p style="text-align: right;">1</p>	
<p>AUTORIZAÇÃO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA EM ÁREA MARINHA PROTEGIDA AUTHORIZATION AREA FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN MARINE PROTECTED AREA</p>		
<p>1. Local onde se desenvolverá o trabalho / ArN of the Study:</p>		
<p>Parque Marinho dos Açores /Azores Marine Park</p>	<p>DLR n2 13/2016/A</p>	<p>[LJ] Reserva Natnal Marinha do campo Hidraternal Lucky Strike (PMA03)</p>
<p>2. Titularas da Autorizado / Authorization Holders:</p>		
<p>Nomes/ Nomes: Marjolaine Matabos</p>		
<p>Nr. Identif Civil/ ID Numbers: 19AL98707</p>		
<p>Instituições / Institutions: Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la MER (IFREMER)</p>		
<p>E-mails: marjolaine.matabos@ifremer.fr</p>		
<p>3. Nome do Projeto / Projet Nome :</p>		
<p>Missao MOMARSAT 2023 do navio L'Atalante</p>		
<p>Mission MOMARSAT 2023, L'Ma/ante</p>		
<p>4. Objetivos / Purinstalling :</p>		
<p>Manutenção anual do observatório EMSO-Açores no Lucky Strike (MAR).</p>		
<p>Yearly maintenance of the EMSO-Azores obseNatory at /ucky Strike (Mid-Atlantic Ridge).</p>		
<p>5. Métodos / Equipamentos a Usar / Methods / Equipments :</p>		
<p>Infraestrutura de investigação marinha EMSO, ROV, PIF, DEAFS, caixa de amostragem, modulas e colonização, amostrador ELFES.</p>		
<p>Marine Research Infrastructure EMSO, ROV, PIF, DEAFS, sampling box, co/onizotio modules, ELFES sompler.</p>		
<p>6. Rcolha da Amostras : / Sample Recolection :</p>		
<p>Fluidos hidrotermais, organismos e microorganismos de Depundidade, rochas, sedimentos e agua do mar.</p>		
<p>Hydrothermal fluids, deep-sea organisms and micro-organisms, racks and sea water.</p>		
<p>7. Duraçio / Duration:</p>		
<p>De 15/06/2023 a 15/09/2023.</p>		
<p>From 15/06/2023 to 15/09/2023.</p>		
<p>10. Condicionantes / Conditions:</p>		
<p>1. No relatório relativo a esta autorização, a enviar até um ano a contar do seu termo à DRPM (info.drpm@azores.gov.pt), deve constar a rota (GPS) do navio, amostras recolhidas e os métodos e equipamentos utilizados. AS atividades descritas no relatório serao alvo de apreciação, nomeadamente quanta aos impactas sobre as espécies e os habitats, podendo ser solicitada informação adicional;</p>		
<p>2. A presente licença nao inibe do cumprimento de qualquer outra legislação aplicavel à açao em curso.</p>		
<p>1. The report relating to this license, to be sent up to one year alter its expiry to DRPM (info.drpm@azores.gov.pt), must contain the route (GPS) of the ship, collected samples and the methods and equipment used. The activities described in the report will be the subject of assessment, namely with regard to impacts on species and habitats, additional information <i>maV</i> be requested;</p>		
<p>2. This lic:ense daes not prevent /rom complying with any other legislation applic:able to the c:urrent action.</p>		
<p>O DIRETOR REGIONAL, THEREGIONALDIRECTOR,</p>		
<p>Auinado por: MARIO RUIRILHO OEPINHO Data: 2023.06.16 15:50:1<ft-00'00' Ce-rific:ado por: Governo R-regional dos Açores Atributos c-ertificados: Diretor R-e9ion+Ide Políticas MarAimas</p>		
<p>CARTAa LJ CIJADAJ</p>		
<p>SGC0060/2023/4718</p>		

R.

MINISTÉRIO DOS NEGÓCIOS ESTRANGEIROS
Direção-Geral de Política Externa

Ref.a 86621/2023

Proc.º DGPE/USEN-24/2023 04/07/2023

NOTA VERBAL

O Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros apresenta os seus melhores cumprimentos à Embaixada de França em Lisboa e, em referência à Nota Verbal nº 2023 -0053404, de 01.02.2023, tem a honra de informar que é autorizada a entrada na **ZEE** portuguesa subarea dos Açores, do navio oceanográfico **L'ATALANTE**, bem como a campanha de investigação **MOMARSAT2023**, com início nesta data, até 15 de setembro de 2023, no pressuposto de que serão cumpridos todos os formalismes constantes do Anexo I.

Tenda em conta o relevante interesse da referida campanha, o Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros muito agradece o envio (preferencialmente em formato eletrónico) do respetivo Relatório, assim como dos dados recolhidos.

O Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros aproveita a oportunidade para reiterar à Embaixada de França os protestos da sua mais elevada consideração.

À Embaixada de França em Lisboa

1

15/08/2023

04 (35) 2 11 00 00 Email: dpe@

ANEXO I

1. O NAVIO FRANCÊS "L'ATALANTE" PRETENDE EFETUAR A CAMPANHA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO "MOMARSAT 2023", NO PERÍODO 15 DE JUNHO A 15 DE SETEMBRO DE 2023, DURANTE O QUAL ENTRARÁ NA ZEE PORTUGUESA, SUBÁREA DO CONTINENTE.
2. CONSIDERA-SE QUE A ÁREA DE OPERAÇÕES INTERFERE COM A ZONA DE PASSAGEM DE SUBMARINOS E PSEAS.
3. NÃO OBSTANTE NÃO ESTAR CALENDARIZADA NENHUMA NAVEGAÇÃO SUBMARINA NO PERÍODO CONSIDERADO, TORNA-SE NECESSÁRIO TER CONHECIMENTO COM 72 HORAS DE ANTECEDÊNCIA DAS INTENÇÕES DE MOVIMENTOS E POSIÇÕES DE TRABALHO DO NAVIO FRANCÊS, POR FORMA A GARANTIR A SEGURANÇA DA NAVEGAÇÃO SUBMARINA NACIONAL E ESTRANGEIRA.
4. PARA ESTE EFEITO O NAVIO DEVERÁ MANTER O AIS SEMPRE EM FUNCIONAMENTO E EFETUAR UM COMUNICADO DIÁRIO, DIRIGIDO AO CENTRO DE OPERAÇÕES MARÍTIMAS (COMAR), COMA SEGUINTE INFORMAÇÃO:
 - A. IDENTIFICAÇÃO DO NAVIO.
 - B. POSIÇÃO/RUMO/VELOCIDADE REFERIDA ÀS 12.00Z.
 - C. ATIVIDADE EM CURSO/POSIÇÕES DE EQUIPAMENTOS FUNDEADOS.
 - D. INTENÇÕES PROXIMAS 24, 48 E 72 HORAS.
 - E. NR. TELEX/INMARSAT FAXE TELEFONE/EMAIL NAVIO.
5. SOLICITA-SE, AINDA, QUE SEMPRE QUE HOUVER ALTERAÇÃO AOS DADOS DO PLANEAMENTO, ESTA SEJA COMUNICADA COM A MÁXIMA ANTECEDÊNCIA POSSÍVEL, DESEJAVELMENTE COM 72 HORAS E NUNCA MENOS DE 24 HORAS.
6. PARA PASSAGEM DA INFORMAÇÃO ACIMA REFERIDA, PODEM SER UTILIZADOS OS SEGUINTE MEIOS:
 - A. TELEFONE 351 210 984 451
 - B. E-MAIL comar.supervisor@marinha.pt E CENTRO DE COORDENAÇÃO DE BUSCA E SALVAMENTO MARÍTIMO DE PONTA DELGADA (TELEFONE 00351 296 281 777; czma.pc.supervisor@marinha.pt).
7. NO DECURSO DOS TRABALHOS DE INVESTIGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA, DESIGNADAMENTE DURANTE AS OPERAÇÕES DE MANUSEAMENTO DOS EQUIPAMENTOS, OUTROS MATERIAIS SUBMERSOS E BÓIAS DE SINALIZAÇÃO, BEM COMO NAS MANOBRAS A QUE O NAVIO ESTIVER SUJEITO, DEVEM SER SALVAGUARDADAS AS DISTÂNCIAS MÍNIMAS DE SEGURANÇA QUER AOS CABOS SUBMARINOS (1/4 MILHA) IDENTIFICADOS NAS CARTAS NAUTICAS OFICIAIS, QUER AOS NAVIOS (1 MILHA) ENVOLVIDOS EM REPARAÇÕES OU LANÇAMENTOS DE CABOS.
8. DE FORMA A EMITIR ATEMPADAMENTE OS AVISOS À NAVEGAÇÃO, O COMAR DEVERÁ SER INFORMADO DOS MOVIMENTOS E LIMITAÇÕES DE MANOBRA DO NAVIO COM 24H DE ANTECEDÊNCIA, ATRAVÉS DO SEGUINTE E-MAIL: COMAR_SEGMAR@MARINHA.PT.
9. SOLICITA-SE RELATÓRIO DE MISSÃO, METADADOS OBTIDOS, BEM COMO A RESPECTIVA META-INFORMAÇÃO; DADOS BATIMÉTRICOS (RAW E PROCESSADOS) E OUTRAS INFORMAÇÕES PERTINENTES PARA APOIAR A CONCLUSÃO DO PROGRAMA SEAMAO 2030, DESCRIÇÃO PORMENORIZADA DOS EQUIPAMENTOS TÉCNICO-CIENTÍFICOS EMPREGUES NA AQUISIÇÃO DOS DADOS E PROCESSAMENTO DA INFORMAÇÃO, ASSIM COMO A SUA DETALHADA PARAMETRIZAÇÃO.

REGIÃO AUTÔNOMA DOS AÇORES

Vice-Presidência do Governo dos Açores Direção Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia

Acesso e utilização de recursos naturais para fins científicos / Access and use of natural resources for scientific purinstallings

Certificado de Conformidade Internacionalmente Reconhecido

ADENDA

**International/ly Rec.ogni'l,etl Complümce Certificate
ATUALIZAÇÃO / UPDATE**

CCIR-RAA/2023/35

A TODO O TEMPO O TITULAR PODE FICAR OBRIGADO A: / THE HOLDER MAY AT ANY TIME BE OBUGED TO:

- a) **Depositar ou remeter duplicado da amostra**, ou parte dela, no prazo e local a determinar pela entidade emissora da declaração, nos termos do disposto no n.º 1 do artigo 11.º do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Deposit or send a duplicate of the sample, or part of it, within the time and place lobe delennined by the entity issuing the declaration; pursuant to paragraph 1 of article 11 of the Regional Legislative Decree No. 9/2012 IA, of March 20th, with the changes introduced by Regiona/Legislative Decree No. 17/2020 IA, of July 15th;*
- b) **Enviar o relatório** a que se refere o n.º 2 do artigo 11.º do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Submit the report refered to in paragraph 2 of article 11 of the Regional Legis/a/ive Decree no. 9/2012 IA, of Mar-ch 20, with the changes introduced byRegional Legislative Decree no. 17/2020IA, of July 15;*
- c) **Contratualizar mecanismos de cooperação coma RA..4.**, nos termos do disposto no artigo 17.º-B do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Contract cooperation mechanisms with the RAA,pursuant to article 17-B of the Regional Legislative Dec,-ee No. 9/2012 IA, of March 20, witli the changes introduced by Regional Legislative Decree No. 17/2020/A, of July 15;*
- d) **Realizar um contrato de partilha justa e equitativa de benefícios** nos termos do disposto no artigo 17.º-C do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Carry out a/air-agreement for theJust and equitable sharing ofbenefits; Enter into a fair and equitable bene.fit sharing agreement under the terms of article 17;*
- e) **Não permitir a utilização da amostra, ou de parte dela, por terceiros**, exceto nos casos de procedimento de transferência previstos no capítulo III do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho. *Do not allow the use of the sample, or part of it, by third parties, except in cases of transfer procedure providedfor ir, Chapter III ofRegionaJ Leeislative Decree No. 9/2012/ A, o(March 20, with the clzanees introduced by Rel,ional Lefislative Decree No. 17/2020! A, of July 15.*

TITULAR DO CCIR / DECLARATION OWNER

CRUTSE: Missão MOM ARSAT 2023 do navio L'Atalante
CIENTISTA CHEFE DO CRUZEIRO: Marjolaine Matabos

Nº de Identificação Civil/Passaporte: Nalio11alldel11ity CanVpassport: 19AL98707

Endereço/Address: 1625 route de St Anne Technopole Brest-Iroise ; **Codigo Postal/Zip code:** 29280 - França

Instituição/Institution: Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la MER (IFREMER)

EQUIPA ENVOLVIDA NAS ATIVIDADES DE ACFSSO/ IDENTIFICATION OF THE TEAM INVOLVED IN ACCE ACTIVITIES:

Colaborador/Investigador Collaborator/Researcher	Atividade Depis;-ional/ Occupation	Nº de Jdentificação Civil/Passaporte Nalio11al ldel11ity Card/Passport	Instituição/ Institution
Matjolaine Matabos	Cientista Chefe	19AL98707	IFREMER
Ana.Colaço	Cientista	09542412	IMAR Okeanos -Uni V. Açore
GAYET Nicolas	Chemistry, Instrwnentation	19FD94874	Ifremer
SARRAZIN Jozée	Ecology	4AY29394	Ifremer
MERTZ Nicolas	Infrastructure	130755100395	Ifremer
Damien SALIOU	Infrastructure	210129453749	Ifremer
Laurent GAUTIER	Infrastructure	2910041402291007842	Ifremer
Cyprien LEMARECHAL	Cientista	181135352033	
Mathilde CANNAT	Geophysics	13CP38111	IPGP
HAUTEMA YOU David	Cientista	18AC18269	

Direç o Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia•Rua do Mercado, 21 • 9500-126 Ponta Delgada Telefone: (+351) 296 308 900 (geral) •

E-mail: info.drct@azores.gov.pt scientific.samples@azores.gov.pt